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**JOURNALISTIC FRAMES IN CONSTRUCTIVE NEWS
REPORTING ON EUROPEAN MIGRATION**

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Constructive news framing of the European migration

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ACCEPTANCE PAGE

This Thesis titled "Journalistic Frames in Constructive News Reporting on European Migration" is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Information and Communication Studies, UP Open University, in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the degree Master of Development Communication (MDC).

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ABSTRACT

This research focused on constructive news frames used in reporting the EU migration of 2015. Three journalists who are well-known for using constructive journalism techniques in their work were interviewed to determine these frames. Cathrine Gyldensted, Ulrik Haagerup and Sean Dagan Wood discussed the elements that constitutes a Constructive Journalism story, the frames that were used in stories about European migration, whether constructive or not. Constructive frames were then summarized in HASH: History, Ability, Solution and Human story. The structure of the constructive news story focusing on European migration formed the WDIET method: What Now, Data, Impact, Empathy and Truth.

These frames and elements can help practicing journalists in their reports, whether these are about the European migration or any other phenomenon in society that includes mass movement of people, stereotypes and questions of heritage.#

PREFACE

This thesis focused on constructive news frames present in journalistic reporting about the European migration. The topic is important if we consider how big migration is, how it is currently affecting Europe and how long it is still going to continue as a natural phenomenon in human history.

I decided to focus on this topic for my thesis because of my connection with the journalism field, my continued assumption that it can change societies and belief that if it does, it should do its work for progress and not for deterioration.

Journalism's role in shaping our society is beyond anyone's grasp. But just like what an old man once said, “With great power comes great responsibility.” Journalists should keep this in mind as they wield their pens. Especially in issues such as the European migration which can make or break humanity as we know it.

If journalists mirror society, which part of society is that exactly? And where is that reflection leading us to? By describing the frames that constitute a constructive report on European migration, I intend to supplement the current set of tools that good journalists use. As one of my interviewees mentioned, constructive journalism is not a genre but a new way of seeing things. Constructive journalism intends to give balance to the usual news reports that are negatively skewed, which drive readers away disengaging them. How can journalism continue to play an important role in shaping society if there are not enough readers to

influence?

Writing this thesis was a wonderful journey to both the known and the unknown. My interviews made me realize that journalism is truly a wonderful field to work in. I learned new ways of reporting and re-learned journalism like I was back in college.

It was a great experience to talk to Cathrine Gyldensted, Ulrik Haagerup and Sean Dagan Wood who shared the same reflections and feelings about negativity in the news. All interviews were enlightening. I thank them for their time and am honored to be their student in this area.

This thesis changed me not only as a journalist and writer but as a person as well. I am much more aware now of how I frame what I write or what I say, much more aware of the power of words and have never been so solution-focused as now in all my life. When conducting interviews for work, I always add a future-oriented question. I even added the “what now” question in the events summary template which is part of our communication guidelines at work.

It is my hope that journalists, public relations professionals and communication specialists who will read this thesis will also think twice about how they frame their stories and take into account the potential of the future-oriented question. And that journalism schools worldwide will add constructive journalism and the power of framing into account when raising new journalists.#

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Chapter1: Introduction

Migration news dominated European media in 2015. According to the United Nations, “worldwide displacement hit an all-time high in 2015, affecting more than 60 million people.” A little over a million of them arrived in Europe in 2015 by land and sea.

Rationale And Background Of The Study

Images of full rubber boats crossing the Mediterranean, crowds rushing barb-wired fences and crammed trains of Syrian refugees were the pictures of conflict. At the other end of this struggle were faces of children in need of care, broke Greeks who lent a helping hand and Europeans of different colors, shapes and sizes who volunteered to ensure that the refugees who filled the rubber boats reached land safely. In the middle of these two extremes were news reports that included both the negative and the positive sides of the issue citing possible solutions, trying to solve the largest mass migration of modern history. This middle ground is an emerging domain in journalism, a new awareness called constructive journalism.

Cathrine Gyldensted, an investigative journalist herself, conducted the first academic research on constructive journalism. She defined it as:

“Constructive journalism recognizes that faults, failure, and abuse exist in the world; however, it maintains that simultaneously there is always development, growth, and opportunity... Constructive journalism investigates opportunities, looks at dilemmas from all sides, and indicates remedies. It does not ignore the problems and it does not trivialize them; instead it focuses on how these problems can be solved.” (Gyldensted,

2011)

As opposed to just regular news reports which focused on conflict, constructive journalism focuses on solutions and puts a high price on journalism's role in society.

The UK-based Constructive Journalism Project defined constructive journalism as “rigorous, compelling reporting that includes positive and solution-focused elements in order to empower audiences and present a fuller picture of truth, while upholding journalism’s core functions and ethics.”

Constructive journalism has its roots in Denmark and is slowly flourishing in the Netherlands, the United Kingdom and the United States where it is also known as solutions journalism. This approach, or journalism genre as called by some, believes that only reporting the negative or the positive side of a story does not show the whole story. The part that shows solutions and possibilities is half of a story and must be told too. It is believed that by telling the whole story, the public is not only properly informed but more engaged and better armed to make informed decisions. Because of its redeeming factor, this kind of storytelling is apt for crises reporting, crises such as the big EU migration of 2015.

This research focused on how constructive journalism framed the EU migration of 2015 and looked into the motivations of journalists who used constructive journalism in their work. What frames did they use when producing a constructive story about the EU migration? What considerations did they make to frame a story as such? Previous research

has claimed that there were at least five factors that influence d journalists in framing an issue: social norms and values, organizational pressures and constraints, pressures of interest groups, journalistic routines, and ideological or political orientations of journalists (e.g., Shoemaker & Reese,1996; Tuchman, 1978). Are these the same factors that journalists who practice constructive journalism consider in carrying out their work?

The communication angle of this research lies on the fact that it focused on journalism and used framing as the working theory.

News journalism dominates our daily lives. According to one philosopher, it is an “addiction of our daily lives that which we are not aware of” (Wijnberg, 2013). The news informs us of what is happening from the place where we live in to other parts of the world. Beyond information, it communicates to us cultures, beliefs and traditions of other people which we do not know yet of or we might not ever know of personally. It is our window to the world (Tuchman, 1978). To help us make sense of that world, journalists de-constructs events by focusing on details (Johnson-Cartee, 2005). With the amount of information and diversity that we gather from the news, we are able to make better decisions, are able to understand the world beyond the capacity of our sight and the grasp of our hands.

What kind of information do we really get from the news and what kind of world does journalism show us? What does it show of the world in the middle of what probably is the fastest and largest human migration to date using the constructive journalism lens? By focusing on the details that they deem important in the framework that they are used to, did

journalists miss other details that were as important? Any news consumer should know this and any journalist reporting on crises such as the European migration must understand that the reporting creates a reality for the audience.

This research aimed to bring to light two development issues: that of migration, specifically European migration as it happened and heightened in 2015, and the role of journalism in society, characterized by constructive journalism in this study.

Human migration is not a new phenomenon. According to the International Organization of Migration, it “is as old as human history. In fact, in some places on our planet there are migrant routes that have been in continuous use for over 4,000 years.” Early humans left their place of origin for reasons of survival. Since they used to hunt for food, they would move to abundant places for sustenance and where the climate is pleasant. While the modern man still migrates to satisfy hunger, this hunger translates to more than better employment. Many people in our age migrate just to live in a different environment for purposes of discovery and true interest about the world. Ease of travel made this thirst for this kind of knowledge ever more accessible.

However, a natural occurrence such as migration becomes a question of development whenever people leave their places of origin not because they want to but because they have to. Current data from the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees suggest that about 60 million people are displaced worldwide. This displacement is caused by armed conflict, generalized violence and natural disasters. Of the 60 million mentioned, 1,046,599 arrived in

Europe by land and sea in 2015 alone.

Sudden migratory flows become an issue of development due to its unforeseen nature. Receiving countries are caught unprepared and while there are usually measures in place for resettlement, this does not prove enough because of the rapid acceleration of the numbers of people who need help.

This is what is currently happening to Europe. As migrant arrivals advanced in the summer of 2015, Europe did not know how to react. There were financial and spatial questions to consider and according the media, not many European countries were actually welcoming of refugees.

Research Problem

Central to this thesis is news journalism's role in the ongoing debate of the European migrant crisis, or in constructive journalism fashion: the big EU migration. As public perception is important in any issue that grips society and news affects public perception, it is important for journalists to know and note that whatever news they produce about migrants, refugees and asylum seekers can drive the issue to finding a solution or further deepen the conflict. An emerging domain in journalism called constructive journalism in Europe and solutions journalism in the United States hopes to focus on solutions as opposed to conflict which has been the guiding light of journalists in their daily news gathering.

This thesis looked into examples of constructive journalism as it is applied on the

issue of the European migration and answered the following questions –

Main research question:

What journalistic frames are present in constructive news reports on European migration?

Sub-questions:

1. How is constructive news on European migration structured?
2. How do constructive journalism practitioners generate these frames on European migration news?
3. What constructive journalistic frames are most present in constructive news reports on European migration?
4. What constructive journalistic frames are least present in constructive news reports on European migration?
5. What other constructive journalistic frames on European migration can be explored?

Objectives Of The Study

The topic for this study is the constructive news framing of European migration.

The objectives of this study were:

1. to explore how constructive journalism is applied on the issue of European migration,
2. to identify what journalistic frames are present in constructive news on European migration,

3. to discover what considerations constructive journalists make when choosing these frames and why, and
4. to describe how constructive news on European migration is structured.

Significance Of The Study

The world is a big and complex place. To make sense of it, journalists help us understand the world of public affairs beyond our direct experience (Patterson, 2013). They help us fathom challenges that societies face. An example of a challenge is the unforeseen migration of more than a million people to Europe in 2015. It raised many questions regarding migrant settlement and resettlement, is presently causing division and remains unresolved.

This study is significant because of journalism's role in public service. In times of crises, there is more demand for trustworthy and balanced news. By exploring how constructive journalism is applied on the issue of European migration, I brought to light examples of balanced reporting that is solutions-based instead of conflict-based. These examples will help journalists better understand what constructive journalism is.

As well, the identification of constructive journalistic frames present in European migration news will be beneficial for journalists as they will understand which issues to focus on when producing stories on migration or any other issue inundated with negativity and hate.

Discovering the considerations constructive journalists make when choosing these frames and their reasons behind it would strengthen a previous research made on what influences journalists in their choice of news frames (Tuchman, 1978). If additional considerations are detected, it will supplement said research.

Finally, being able to describe how constructive news on European migration is structured will make it easy for journalists to produce constructive stories. In deconstructing constructive news, journalists will who would like to add a constructive layer in their reporting will learn how to construct their own, whether it be about the European migration or any crisis.

In summary, this study will help journalists better understand what constructive journalism is, how it is structured and why it is a good approach when applied to social issues perceived to be filled with conflicts such as that of the European migration. With the growing division amongst EU states on this issue, it is important to explore how journalism can play a more impactful role by using solutions-based frames. This study will benefit journalists, news consumers and the society as a whole.

Scope And Limitations Of The Study

Scope.

This study investigated constructive news framing of European migration. It explored how constructive journalism was applied on the issue of European migration, identified what journalistic frames were present in constructive news on European migration, discovered

what considerations constructive journalists made when choosing these frames and why and described how constructive news on European migration was structured.

The scope of the study is constructive news framing as applied to the issue of European migration. This means that no other news frames were examined except for constructive news frames. Moreover, no other news event was considered besides European migration.

To achieve solid results for this study, it took the form of qualitative research using semistructured qualitative interviewing. The study population for this research were practitioners of constructive journalism located in Europe and involved with the production of news stories on the European migration using the constructive journalism approach. This population is chosen due to the location of circumstance (European migration) and the researcher.

Limitations.

To fulfill the needs of the scope of this study, data gathering was done through qualitative interviews with journalists who practiced constructive journalism and who were involved in the production of news stories on the European migration.

In qualitative interviewing, the quality of data depending on the quality of the interviewer and interviewee, hence, rapport building; the skill of the interviewer in asking questions and the ability of the interviewees to express themselves openly are of primary

importance. If the rapport between the interviewer and interviewee is unpleasant, there could be information neglected. If the interviewer is not skilled in conducting interviews, the research questions may not be answered properly. If the interviewee cannot express him/herself thoroughly, answers may be interpreted incorrectly. However, these limitations are at a minimum as the interviewer is an experienced journalist herself and is aware of rapport-building and proper preparation.

Another limitation is the time that qualitative interviewing takes. The interviewer had to make appointments that fit with the schedule of the interviewee and the school year when the study should be conducted and finished.

Chapter 2: Review of Related Literature

As this study investigated constructive news framing of the European migration, it connected three domains: that of constructive journalism, news framing and European migration. Keywords used for primary literature search were *media and migration*, *European migration*, *European migrant crisis* and *European refugee crisis*. This search was useful to introduce European migration and media's relationship with migrants and the migration issue in general.

To understand the theory of framing, the researcher used the keywords *news framing*, *media framing*, *framing theory* and *framing analysis*. Since framing is a popular communication theory, this search showed countless results. However, only literature related to the subjects of news journalism's role in constructing reality were considered for the literature review.

The researcher also searched literature related with constructive journalism by using the keywords *constructive journalism*, *constructive news*, *slow journalism*, *positive journalism*, *positive news* and *peace journalism*. Below is a list of related studies, synthesis of available literature and the research gap that this study will fill.

Related Studies, Research Gap And Synthesis Of Available Literature

With constructive journalism being an emerging domain, there were only two known

dissertations and two books written about it at the time the research was conducted.

The two known dissertations were Cathrine Gyldensted's *Innovating news journalism through positive psychology* and Karen McIntyre's *Constructive journalism: The effects of positive emotions and solution information in news stories*. The two known books were Cathrine Gyldensted's *From mirrors to movers: five elements of positive psychology in constructive journalism* and Ulrik Haagerup's *Constructive news*.

Cathrine Gyldensted's *Innovating news journalism through positive psychology* was the starting point for her book *From mirrors to movers: five elements of positive psychology in constructive journalism*. In her thesis, she argued that while minimizing harm is part of the journalists' code of ethics, this is not reflected in the news stories that mainstream media produce. She claimed that this is the reason why there are less news consumers. She further suggested that journalists must innovate not in using new gadgets or further digitizing of content but in how they write their stories. She recommended that this innovation happen through the use of positive psychology in the products that journalists produce.

Karen McIntyre's *Constructive journalism: The effects of positive emotions and solution information in news stories* is the very first PhD dissertation published on constructive journalism and its connections with positive psychology. She called constructive journalism “a way to rehabilitate journalism, given the field’s steady stream of negative, conflict-based news that has resulted in weary news audiences, among other undesirable effects.” In her dissertation, she tested how audiences react to constructive stories – which

left the public feeling better and which left them engaged to the point of wanting to solve a problem.

The two books published on the subject were both authored by journalists from Denmark where it started growing roots: *Constructive News* (2014) by Ulrik Haagerup and *From Mirrors to Movers* by Cathrine Gyldensted. Haagerup is the Executive Director of Danish Broadcasting, Denmark's oldest and largest broadcaster. Gyldensted is also a journalist from Danish Broadcasting with a master's degree in Applied Positive Psychology. With her master's thesis titled *Innovating journalism through the use of positive psychology*, she originated the idea of connecting journalism and psychology as having a strong potential for innovation.

Both books and Gyldensted's thesis brought into light the ability of news media to provide negative emotional impact to those who consume it. Haagerup's first chapter is aptly titled, "Why are you so negative?" telling of his experiences at social circles where, when he starts talking to people about his profession, they ask him why media people always tell negative stories. He ends up defending his bread and butter of course, telling people back that, well, journalists are just doing their jobs. If negative stories dominate the news, it is because there is more negativity dominating every day. But after some self-reflection, he ended up asking himself: "Is the world really like that? What on earth are we doing?"

He proceeded: "Is our journalistic glass always half empty or half full? Do our routines and habits and our view of the world lead us to paint an overly negative picture of

the world, because the criteria we use to select items of ‘news’ from the information torrent lead us to focus instinctively on things that aren’t working: the people who lose out, the people who are to blame, and the drama that surrounds them?"

Gyldensted shared Haagerup’s reflection. In her years of investigative journalism, she also ended up asking herself the same questions. In her thesis, she wrote: "I began to doubt whether my work made a positive difference for society, people, and communities. It seemed to me that I was mostly inducing negative affect and consequently actively corroded society. When we hold others accountable, we should hold ourselves accountable too. When we pride ourselves in being anti-authoritarian towards authority, we should exercise that anti-authority on ourselves and thus question our own rules, habits and self-perception on a regular basis weeding out habitual thinking and foster new ideas. First step then is critically revisiting our own foundational principles, journalism’s ethics code, its historical roots and empirically investigate how we in the news media hold up to honouring the code."

Haagerup’s book was full of data that showed how much negative news is published compared to constructive news and how constructive news has changed the Danish media landscape. Gyldensted, in her book, showed more examples of constructive journalism in other countries, such as The Netherlands and the United Kingdom. Gyldensted also shared how journalists can apply constructive journalism in their work by changing their line of questioning. Instead of asking only for the who, what, when, where, why and how, Gyldensted added another W to the set: “what now?”

I argue that this additional W (what now) gives constructive news frames their form. Answers to 'what now' questions point to solutions which is one of the main characteristics of constructive journalism. I believe that this characteristic provides the organizing elements to constructive stories on European migration, hence, constructive news frames.

News frames or framing is a favorite topic in communication journals. Therefore, my literature search provided a more productive search. The challenge was to choose fitting literature that will help understand the theory and how to apply it in the process of this research. The literature qualified to understand the theory better is Dietram Scheufele's *Framing as a theory of media effects* published by the *Journal of Communication*. The literature that illustrated the use of framing in news journalism are Walter Lippmann's *Public Opinion*, Gaye Tuchman's *Making the news* and Karen Johnson-Cartee's *News narratives and news framing: constructing political reality*. The literature found fit to understand the application of news framing theory are Paul D'Angelo et al.'s *Doing news framing analysis: empirical and theoretical perspectives* and Stephen Reese et al.'s *Framing public life*. These pieces of literature stem from the earlier and seminal works of Erving Goffman *The presentation of self in everyday life* and *Frame analysis: an essay on the organization of experience*.

Journalist Walter Lippmann first connected framing with the practice of journalism in his seminal work *Public Opinion* (1921). He referred to the effects of framing as *pictures in our heads*:

“Looking back we can see how indirectly we know the environment in which nevertheless we live. We can see that the news of it comes to us now fast, now slowly; but that whatever we believe to be a true picture, we treat as if it were the environment itself. It is harder to remember that about the beliefs upon which we are now acting, but in respect to other peoples and other ages we flatter ourselves that it is easy to see when they were in deadly earnest about ludicrous pictures of the world. We insist, because of our superior hindsight, that the world as they needed to know it, and the world as they did know it, were often two quite contradictory things.”

Lippmann argued that the news constructs a limited reality. Ergo, those who consume it do not see the whole picture themselves. Gaye Tuchman must have picked up from Lippmann's arguments on her *Making the news* (1978), a significant work on the issue of framing and news as construction of reality. She referred to the news as a frame and window to the world with which the public (at the time of publication, she only referred to them as Americans) “learn of themselves and others, of their own institutions, leaders and life styles and those of other nations and their peoples... the news aims to tell us what we want to know, need to know and should know.”

She discussed further how the window she referred to is problematic since it depends on how it is put together and presented. She also argued that the complexity of news organizations and professional concerns of journalists all have an impact into that frame. However, she added that framing is essential in journalistic practice since it is what organizes

everyday reality and in turn helps journalists make sense of the events they cover.

Johnson-Cartee in her *News narratives and news framing* (2005) claimed that news is a product and is the outcome of a social construction process. She took the 'news as construction of reality theory' to a next level by expounding on Molotch and Lester's (1974) three major news stages in the construction of news: news promoters, news assemblers and news consumers. Johnson-Cartee referred to them as actors in news construction. She also claimed that journalists use framing in their daily work, whether they are aware of it or not.

The news has been framing the migration issue for years, whether consciously or unconsciously. Its power to communicate powerful words and images has guided public opinion on the issue. It has provided images in our heads that we might not be able to shake off, ever. Test it by examining which pictures dominate your mind when you think about Syrian people migrating to Europe. Which images fill your head when recalling stories related to these migrants? How do these images affect your opinion about migration in general?

Numerous researchers (e.g. Briant et al., 2013; Kamenova, 2014) have proven media's relationship with the issue of migration and the creation of more tension than needed.

Emma Briant et al.'s *Bad news for refugees* proved through in-depth interviewing and content analysis that there is a partial and incorrect reporting on migrants, refugees and asylum seekers. The authors pointed out the hostile coverage, imbalance reporting and

confusion amongst the words refugees, asylum seekers and economic migrants as reasons for isolating and stigmatizing migrants. The authors recommended that news journalists respond to migration issues differently than adding conflict. They suggested that there be more attention given in stories about responding to the needs of refugees or pointing to the West as creating the environment for forced migrations.

Denitza Kamenova discussed how media's representation of what she called the other-migrant (e.g. illegal immigrants, refugees, asylum seekers) shaped society's perception and tolerance of them in her publication *Media and othering: How media discourse on migrants reflects and affects society's tolerance*.

Media's ability to manufacture conflict in times of crisis has also been often studied along with the impact of news coverage on conflict (e.g. Gilboa, 2007; Pauly, 2009; Reuben, 2009; Schneider, 2009; de Vreese et al., 2015).

Claes de Vreese et al.'s *Manufacturing conflict? How journalists intervene in the conflict frame building process* specifically looked into how journalists actively exaggerate conflict by the words and images they use.

Constructive journalism deals with the other side of crisis reporting. It magnifies solutions instead of conflict and puts the spotlight on the survivors rather than the victims.

Gyldensted wrote in her book *From mirrors to movers*: "We live in a world with a lot

of far-reaching and complex problems and crises. Journalism should reflect that but also facilitate the discussion on possible solutions, challenges and visions. Facilitate the debate on solutions."

If journalism has the ability to manufacture conflict, it also has the power to facilitate the debate on solutions. There are a number of journalists who do this and this research tried to find out how they did it. This research found out where they put the lens in the stories they produced about the European migration.

The main catalyst for this study was the fact that there were currently no available literature addressing constructive news frames focusing on the issue of European migration.

This thesis connected three important domains which were the study of communications, news framing and European migration and will fill the following research gaps:

1. the lack of a scholarly definition of constructive news framing,
2. the absence of an academic research that explores the application of constructive journalism on the issue of European migration,
3. the lack of a study that identifies journalistic frames present in constructive news on European migration,
4. the absence of a scholastic inquiry to discover what considerations constructive journalists make when choosing constructive news frames and the reasons behind it, and

5. the lack of a scholarly analysis on the structural description of constructive news.

Theoretical Framework

The nature of the research that was conducted for this thesis was guided by the framing theory. Framing is one of the most popular communication theories that almost no communication journal is currently published without a paper on the topic. It is a perspective used in political communications, organizations and journalistic productions.

Sociologist Erving Goffman first popularized framing in his publication *The presentation of self in everyday life* (1956). He referred to framing literally as a framework. He claimed that how an individual acts guides other people's impression of said individual.

Robert Entman's definition of the concept is most appropriate when related to the study of communication. He defined framing as “selecting and highlighting some facets of events or issues and making connections among them so as to promote a particular interpretation, evaluation, and/or solution” (Entman, 2004).

Through the years, framing has been called a concept, a domain, an approach, a perspective, a process and an analytical technique (e.g. De Vreese, 2005; D'Angelo, 2010). Gathering from these various definitions, I simply define framing as “how a message is packaged influences how it is understood”.

Journalists stand in the middle of this message packaging. De Vreese et al. (2015)

were even able to prove that journalists do take an active and conscious role in framing conflict. Researchers (e.g. Tuchman, 1978; Gans, 1979; Shoemaker & Reese, 1996) have long identified why journalists frame an issue the way they do. Five influences have been specified: (1) social norms and values, (2) ideology and prejudice, (3) organizational routines, (4) promoters or elites and (5) interest groups.

The following theoretical framework connects framing and its influences with journalistic work and the basic communication model:

This theoretical framework is rooted from the most basic communication model which used the sender→message→ receiver approach (Adler & Towne, 1978). It is then connected with the three main actors that Johnson-Cartee specified: the promoters on the left along with other framing influences, the assembler (or sender in the basic communication framework) and the consumer (or receiver in the basic communication framework).

This framework further brought to light what other researchers have cited as media

frames and individual frames (e.g. Scheufele, 1999). Media frames were the elements that practitioners in the industry used to organize their thoughts, promoters' ideas and other framing influences. Individual frames refer to internal frames that an individual also has in him/her as part of personal ideologies that could be brought about by e.g. upbringing or social connections.

I added another layer to these studies which, in my mind, completed the framework for this research. These are the boxes labeled conflict-focused and solutions-focused. I argue that the news being a product of individual and media frames, can take two paths: conflict-focused and solutions-focused. While most news stories are conflict-based, constructive journalism is solutions-based and this research looked into the framing of news that produces such stories using European migration as its perimeter.

Analytical Framework

Framing theory basically claims that how a message is packaged influences how it is understood. After connecting the three concepts of constructive journalism, news framing and European migration, I have come up with the following analytical framework:

This framework started with the thesis topic and central idea which is: constructive news framing of European migration. It then deconstructed the three domains to explain their relationship with one another being the three main parts of this research. First came the concept of news on European migration. This referred to all news reports produced on

European migration. These reports were divided into those produced using traditional journalism and those that were developed using the constructive journalism approach.

You will notice the difference between traditional journalism and constructive journalism with the questions journalists ask. While journalists focus on the past and the present asking the who, what, when, where and how questions, those who practice constructive journalism understand the potential behind the future-oriented question: “what now?”. When reporting about a crisis such as the European migration, asking only questions that pertain to the past and the present lead to stories which are conflict-focused. Adding the “what now” question provides the constructive layer that leads to stories which are solutions-

focused. Asking different questions lead to contrasting frames. In the end, these frames define the news produced about European migration.

This study will only focus on the constructive frames which is the reason behind the darker coloring of this approach in the above framework.

Definition Of Terms

To make sure that the reader/s of this research understand it the same way that the author wrote it, I have come up with the definition of the terms used all throughout this report. The terms are presented in alphabetical order for easy searching:

Constructive journalism – rigorous, compelling reporting that includes positive and solution-focused elements in order to empower audiences and present a fuller picture of truth, while upholding journalism’s core functions and ethics

Country of origin – The country that is a source of migratory flows (regular or irregular).

European migrant crisis – (also European migration crisis or European refugee crisis) Refers to the crossing of more than a million migrants and refugees into Europe in 2015, sparking a crisis as countries struggled to cope with the influx, and creating division in the EU over how best to deal with resettling people.

Frame, framing – The way in which the news media organize reality for presentation to the public. News frames are employed by journalists, via tools of language – such as metaphors, exemplars (or historical lessons), catchphrases, depictions and visual images – to impose order on the social world so as to render its happenings into a series of meaningful events.

In-depth interviewing – see **Qualitative interviewing**.

Journalism – The broad range of activities associated with newsmaking. Referenced in the 1700s in France by Denis Diderot as the ‘work of a society of scholars’, the word ‘journalism’ was later applied to the printed reportage of current events. In contemporary usage, it refers to the organized and public collection, processing and distribution of news and current affairs material.

Migration – The movement of a person or a group of persons, either across an international border, or within a State. It is a population movement, encompassing any kind of movement of people, whatever its length, composition and causes; it includes migration of refugees, displaced persons, economic migrants, and persons moving for other purposes, including family reunification.

Migrant – Any person who is moving or has moved across an international border or within a State away from his/her habitual place of residence, regardless of (1) the person’s legal status; (2) whether the movement is voluntary or involuntary; (3) what the causes

for the movement are; or (4) what the length of the stay is. IOM concerns itself with migrants and migration-related issues and, in agreement with relevant

States, with migrants who are in need of international migration services.

Qualitative interviewing – also called In-Depth Interviews include both individual interviews (e.g., one-on-one) as well as "group" interviews (including focus groups). The data can be recorded in a wide variety of ways including stenography, audio recording, video recording or written notes. In depth interviews differ from direct observation primarily in the nature of the interaction. In interviews it is assumed that there is a questioner and one or more interviewees. The purpose of the interview is to probe the ideas of the interviewees about the phenomenon of interest.

Receiving country – Country of destination or a third country. In the case of return or repatriation, also the country of origin. Country that has accepted to receive a certain number of refugees and migrants on a yearly basis by presidential, ministerial or parliamentary decision.

Refugees – A person who, "owing to a well-founded fear of persecution for reasons of race, religion, nationality, membership of a particular social group or political opinions, is outside the country of his nationality and is unable or, owing to such fear, is unwilling to avail himself of the protection of that country.

Resettlement – The relocation and integration of people (refugees, internally

displaced persons, etc.) into another geographical area and environment, usually in a third country. In the refugee context, the transfer of refugees from the country in which they have sought refuge to another State that has agreed to admit them. The refugees will usually be granted asylum or some other form of long-term resident rights and, in many cases, will have the opportunity to become naturalized.

Solutions journalism – Rigorous and compelling reporting about responses to social problems.

Chapter 3: Methodology

Before explaining the methodology for this research, it is important to go back to the topic of this study, the objectives and research questions.

The topic for this study is the constructive news framing of European migration.

The objectives of this study were:

1. to explore how constructive journalism is applied on the issue of European migration,
2. to identify what journalistic frames are present in constructive news on European migration,
3. to discover what considerations constructive journalists make when choosing these frames and why, and
4. to describe how constructive news on European migration is structured.

To fulfill these objectives, this thesis answered the following questions –

Main research question:

What journalistic frames are present in constructive news reports on European migration?

Sub-questions:

1. How is constructive news on European migration structured?
2. How do constructive journalism practitioners generate these frames on European

migration news?

3. What constructive journalistic frames are most present in constructive news reports on European migration?
4. What constructive journalistic frames are least present in constructive news reports on European migration?
5. What other constructive journalistic frames on European migration can be explored?

To answer the research questions, this study took the form of a qualitative inquiry using the case study approach. The primary data gathering procedure for this study was the semistructured qualitative interviewing with constructive journalism practitioners in Europe as the study population.

Research Design

Qualitative inquiry is a research method in which the inquirer explores a central phenomenon, asks participants broad, general questions and collects detailed views of participants in the forms of words or images (Creswell, 2007). It is used when a deeper understanding of a topic is needed.

There are five approaches used in qualitative inquiry: case study, ethnography, grounded theory, narrative and phenomenology. Among these approaches, the case study approach fits the research best. John Creswell's (2007) defined case study as:

“Case study research is a qualitative approach in which the investigator explores a

bounded system (a case) or multiple bounded systems (cases) over time, through detailed, in-depth collection involving multiple sources of information (e.g., observations, interviews, audiovisual material, and documents and reports) and reports a case description and case-based themes.”

Case study is the appropriate method when the researcher has well-defined cases with boundaries and seeks to provide an in-depth understanding of the cases or comparison of several cases (Creswell, 2007).

In this study, the case was that of constructive news framing of the European migration issue through semistructured qualitative interviewing involving journalists who practice constructive journalism.

Locale, Respondents, Sampling Scheme

Taking the research questions into consideration, the sample was chosen according to the following criteria:

- active in the practice of constructive journalism,
- has produced a story (written or multimedia) on the European migration using the constructive journalism approach,
- based in Europe, and
- available for face-to-face or electronic (e.g. Skype, Viber) interview in the duration of the research.

Considering said criteria, these constructive journalism practitioners (sample) were

invited for an interview:

1. Cathrine Gyldensted, former Investigative Journalist, DR Broadcasting / Author, *From mirrors to movers* and *Innovating news journalism through positive psychology*
2. Ulrik Haagerup, Executive News Director, DR Broadcasting / Author, *Constructive news*
3. Ute Schaeffer, Editor-in-chief, Deutsche Welle
4. Katharine Viner, Editor-in-chief, The Guardian
5. Rob Wijnberg, Founder, De Correspondent / Author, *De nieuwsfabriek*
6. Sean Dagan Wood, Founder, Constructive Journalism Project

This sample changed in the duration of the research depending on interviewees' availability.

Data Gathering Procedures

This research used two data gathering procedures. The primary procedure was semistructured qualitative interviewing. The secondary procedure was the examination of previous research on constructive journalism and news framing. Own research of experts interviewed also formed part of the data gathering procedures.

Interviewees were invited via email or telephone with the researcher explaining what the research was all about, the goals of the interview, how long the interview may last and the possible time and date when it will be conducted. Interviews took the form of a semistructured qualitative interview. This approach was chosen to give space for spontaneity

which was important in creating rapport between interviewer and interviewee. Rapport-building is very important in qualitative interviews to ensure that interviewees are able to express themselves openly and hand over all pertinent information to the researcher.

To ensure that the answers of the interviewees were useful for the study, open-ended questions were used. While there was space for spontaneity and follow-up questions, the following questions were asked all interviewees to ensure uniformity and make sure that the research questions were properly covered:

1. How would you define constructive news?
2. Why is it important? Why the shift?
3. Can you give me examples of the constructive reporting that you do?
4. How do you source your constructive stories? What elements do you consider? How does the production of a story go?
5. Is there room for objectivity in constructive reporting? How do you control biases?
6. Have you also been applying this to the issue of the European migration? (If not, what do you intend to do about it?)
7. Where do you put the lens when it comes to the issue of the European migration? What topics do you pursue?
8. If you were to name the issue at hand, would you have named it the European migrant crisis?
9. What should be changed when reporting about the European migration? What topics are we missing?
10. If constructive journalism has been used since European migration started, how would

it have changed the situation?

The interviews lasted 60 to 120 minutes, depending on the rapport between the interviewer and interviewee and the time that the interviewee can spare. The interviews were audio and/or video recorded and in writing, depending on with which the interviewees were most comfortable with. Before the recording was done, interviewees were formally asked for their permission.

All interviews were transcribed and sent to interviewees for validation. After validation and analysis, research writing followed. The transcribed interview were attached to this thesis as appendices as needed and with proper permission of the interviewees.

Data Analysis

With the data gathering procedure taking the form of semistructured qualitative interviewing, the data gathered for this research depended on the quality of the interviews. To analyze the data properly, the interviews were transcribed by the interviewer, validated by the interviewees and organized by the researcher in themes. By themes, I mean similar topics that the interviewees point to when asked the following questions:

1. Can you give me examples of the constructive reporting that you do?
2. How do you source your constructive stories? What elements do you consider? How does the production of a story go?
3. Have you also been applying this to the issue of the European migration? (If not, what do you intend to do about it?)

4. Where do you put the lens when it comes to the issue of the European migration?

What topics do you pursue?

5. What should be changed when reporting about the European migration? What topics are we missing?

The above-mentioned questions were important for the researcher to know which topics the journalists focused on. These topics determined the frames that they used in constructive reporting on the topic of the European migration.

Chapter 4: Findings

To stay true to the goal of this master's thesis of presenting answers to research questions, I would like to present my findings by answering the following:

Main research question:

What journalistic frames are present in constructive news reports on European migration?

Sub-questions:

1. How is constructive news on European migration structured?
2. How do constructive journalism practitioners generate these frames on European migration news?
3. What constructive journalistic frames are most present in constructive news reports on European migration?
4. What constructive journalistic frames are least present in constructive news reports on European migration?
5. What other constructive journalistic frames on European migration can be explored?

What journalistic frames are present in constructive news reports on European migration?

The journalistic frames present in constructive news reports can be summarized into HASH – Human story, Ability, Solution and Historical:

HUMAN STORY – this frame touches on the fact that migrants are human beings, this frame delves heavily on empathy.

Sean Dagan Wood defined it as:

Framing things in a way where we are reminded that this is an issue involving human beings.

ABILITY – can also be called the resource frame where constructive news stories do not see migrants as victims but people with resources and try to answer the following questions:

- How can migrants strengthen the (destination) country's societal structure?
- How can they be a positive addition to our society?
- Do we see migrants as people who lost everything or people that bring skills or resources or inspiration or anything else?

As Cathrine Gyldensted put it,

expanding our view on these human beings, sources, is first step... it's gonna inform and inspire the questions you ask, so the interviewing. Try to not see them as one big group. Try to make individual distinctions.

SOLUTION – this frame informs the 'what now' question that is characteristic of every constructive news story.

Cathrine Gyldensted explained it as,

This is reality, what do we do about it? What now? Be critical around it. Is it easy? If it's not easy, what needs to be done to secure the success of migration and does it have anything to do with how one culture meets another?

HISTORICAL – this frame uses historical facts to put the situation into perspective. Stories on European migration using this frame will use a previous situation that is similar to the current situation.

Ulrik Haagerup made the perfect example of using this frame for a story on European migration shown on DR TV:

One story was during the big migration crisis or refugee crisis last fall, where everybody, including politicians were completely in panic over what to do about all these. We thought it was interesting to go down history to see if can we learn from this. We went to Senegal and did a story about a refugee crisis in 2006 which most people had forgotten about but in 2006, a lot, thousands of people from West Africa, went to the Canary Islands on small boats in order to get into Europe via Spain. We did the story of “how did they solve that crisis” and they did it where the Spanish government and the Senegalese government started cooperating. The Spanish government gave a lot of money to Senegal in order to prevent people from fleeing because there was development aid and they were helping in the villages so that's

about money but it was also by the joint effort controlling the waters between the Canary Islands of the West African coast and Senegal. And actually, within about a year, they succeeded in stopping all immigrants routes from West Africa to Spain and Europe. Not to say that this is the way to cope with the present crisis but just to say, “we have in history experienced something that looks like this somewhere else and how did they solve it?” So in that way, we raise the quality of the public debate.

How is constructive news on European migration structured?

All interviewees argued that constructive news reports do not differ in the structure of regular news reports. Therefore, we can conclude that constructive news reports can also use the inverted pyramid style like a normal news report. It should answer all the Ws and Hs as in a normal news report as well.

The revealing factors in constructive news reports on European migration though can be summarized in the following characteristics (the WDIET method):

WHAT NOW – the additional W that adds to the usual Who, What, When, Where and Why questions of traditional journalism. It is a future-oriented way of asking questions with the idea of not only presenting what has happened but what we can do about it afterwards. The goal of this question is to facilitate debates to understand the topic better and co-create solutions.

Cathrine Gyldensted's idea on how to do it is:

The best way to do it is of course to start the conversation with the problem as we talked about but then move it to what lies ahead... Use data better and then facilitate a more future-oriented discussion and debate around it... What now? What kind of visions could we have for society in the situation? How can it be achieved? What steps should be taken? Will you do it? When will you do it? Those kinds of questions that drives the thinking and the answers to the future in a productive way.

Ulrik Haagerup is passionate about the idea that it is journalism's role to state the facts and facilitate debates:

Focus news journalism also about tomorrow... try to come up with a solution together, facilitate debates about what to do with it. Constructive news is basically the idea that we have to take back journalism to journalism. Help people make up their own minds by providing facts.

See the world with both eyes and in doing so, we should see the good, we should definitely also see the bad and you can say, traditional news like breaking news as we see it today unfolding, will mainly try to answer the questions of what, where, when.

Ask the what now question: It's saying, we are here but what do we do tomorrow?

How do we cope with this? What have other people done? What are the best practices? We frame the answers by asking new questions.

DATA – The use of data in infographic form helps provide a an overview of the story.

Cathrine Gyldensted pointed to this as a strong ingredient for constructive news stories. She described it more extensively so:

In the data use of the coverage of the migrant crisis, there's a lot of constructivity to be gained. Back to the example of The Economist and then you came with the idea of putting it into an even bigger context. Why not give me an infographic about the level of education? What is the real picture here? Where are these people education-wise? What countries are they coming from? What are the context between it? So I get a more clear overview as a reader. The sincerity of the problem. Or the potential of the migrant so-called crisis. Use data better and then facilitate a more future-oriented

discussion and debate around it.

Data puts things in perspective. Infographic, use a big data on something to create like a graphic or interactive overview of a story. So you click on that and you see the connections and you see the Dutch problem here, the Dutch situation here, European here, Global here. That way to story tell has a lot of constructivity in it because it shows you connections, it shows that things are interacting with each other and it shows nuances and gives citizens better information to act on something... The use of data in infographics is a very strong constructive element.

IMPACT – for a news story to be constructive, the journalist must think of the effect of his/her story on the general public. In this context, we call it 'impact'. A constructive journalist thinks what impact he/she has on the reader.

Sean Dagan Wood described this perfectly:

Realizing the impact of journalism, the impact of framing and the power of story, how we use story to give meaning to our lives, to connect with others, understand our world and so we have to go beyond that idea where we are just reflecting back society in journalism because were not.

We're fact-based, but because we use language, we can't escape the fact that language is not neutral so things are always framed and in creating stories, no one writes an entirely dry story that's purely a list of facts.

So inevitably there is framing, there are storylines, there are emotional picks and drops. They are a means of engaging people. And every choice we make in how we do that has an impact. An important thing is to just be aware of that because it's

inescapable so I think, be aware of values... be aware that it has an impact so just be conscious on how you're doing it. That kind of self-awareness.

It's really about strengthening journalism, it's about taking the wonderful expertise, skills and potential of journalism and the valuable role of journalism in a democratic society and with bringing in more constructive journalism to strengthen its ability to serve that fundamental role in the purpose of democracy of still holding power to account, finding, reporting truth and by showing the full picture and empowering people.

EMPATHY – the Merriam-Webster dictionary describes empathy as “ the feeling that you understand and share another person's experiences and emotions: the ability to share someone else's feelings.” This is also true in constructive journalism when reporting about European migration. The empathy element gives life to the Human story frame.

Sean Dagan Wood made an example of this element as used in the said frame:

We're planning a story on our next issue and we're speaking to a number of refugees who have settled in London, talking to them about their experience of being a refugee and the way we frame it is we photograph them in the place where they first felt at home. So the story is built around that feeling of being at home again, which of course is a huge thing for them to have lost that and it is a big personal journey to get started where you feel at home again somewhere else.

We also ran a story a while ago about an initiative in Berlin where some young people just started offering their spare rooms to refugees and this scheme group and of course, it's not just about supporting the refugee but people with spare rooms. They

really benefit as well. They make friends, they learn, it's cultural integration and they say it's a great thing

TRUE – Truth is one of the basic tenets of journalism. Journalists are obsessed in their search for the truth. Traditional journalism's truth however is negatively skewed while in constructive journalism, truth is balanced. Ulrik Haagerup described it perfectly as 'the best obtainable version of the truth':

Our job is to give people the best obtainable version of the truth. Try to see the world with both eyes and be accurate in and honest in what we try to do and we don't try to move society in a certain direction, we believe in the democracy, which is trying to help people to understand the world better but in doing so, we have to use not only one eye but both of them. Your job is to help people make up their own minds by providing facts. By providing both sides of the story. And yes, you're right, there's no such things as being objective, because, who can be that? But you can try. That's the core of journalism. That is to try. To give people the best obtainable version of the truth.

How do constructive journalism practitioners generate these frames on European migration news?

Constructive journalism practitioners generate constructive frames through the application of a constructive mindset. All interviewees challenged the fact that constructive journalism is a genre. Gyldensted, Haagerup and Wood all said that to engage in constructive reporting, one has to have the mindset for it.

According to Cathrine Gyldensted:

It's just journalism. It's not a genre but a mindset. It's the fundamental outlook on the world that you want it to be more comprehensive. You want it to be more complete. It should be all on the overall fundamental thinking of the journalist.

Ulrik Haagerup called it an old-fashioned mindset:

It's a mindset. You can say that it's a very old-fashioned mindset. It is trying to take journalism back to where it belongs which is to publishers. Publishers publish their stories because they want to do good, they want to serve the community, they don't want to lead the community. They don't want to manipulate the community. They strongly believe that it's important that people make up their own minds. It takes time. It's about culture.

Sean Dagan Wood called the mindset a crucial thing and connected the idea with reflection:

The mindset's the crucial thing. The tools of journalism, they're not different from constructive journalism, it's really the core in how they're applied. Rethink what it is to be a journalist and to come back to what's really driving why you want to be a journalist.

We want to inform people in a way that empowers them to use that information constructively whichever way they choose and leave people feeling informed and inspired and not left feeling cynical.

What constructive journalistic frames are most present in constructive news reports on European migration?

I have earlier listed down the following frames used in constructive news reports as:

- Human story
- Ability
- Solution
- Historical

Of these frames, only one is most present in constructive news reports: the 'ability frame'. All interviewees mentioned this and is best described by Cathrine Gyldensted as:

Do we see them as someone who's lost everything or someone that brings skills or resources or inspiration or anything else? So expanding our view on these human beings, sources, is first step. And if you expand that, it's gonna inform and inspire the questions you ask, so the interviewing.

Since it is mostly used, it can also slowly turn to a negative frame when misused.

Sean Dagan Wood called it the economic frame:

That's making certain values more important than others. It's all about the economy, that that means of exchange is the best of one thing when actually it's about human beings. So I think it's important to not allow that to automatically be the framing... Because then the assumption there is that refugees need to benefit the destination country and the economy.

What constructive journalistic frames are least present in constructive news reports on European migration?

Of all the interviewees, only Ulrik Haagerup referred to the Historical frame which is my basis for concluding that this is the least used constructive frame in European migration.

He stated a story that was broadcast over DR TV which uses this frame:

One story was during the big migration crisis or refugee crisis last fall, where everybody, including politicians were completely in panic over what to do about all these. We thought it was interesting to go down history to see if can we learn from this. We went to Senegal and did a story about a refugee crisis in 2006 which most people had forgotten about but in 2006, a lot, thousands of people from West Africa, went to the Canary Islands on small boats in order to get into Europe via Spain. We did the story of “how did they solve that crisis” and they did it where the Spanish government and the Senegalese government started cooperating. The Spanish government gave a lot of money to Senegal in order to prevent people from fleeing because there was development aid and they were helping in the villages so that's about money but it was also by the joint effort controlling the waters between the Canary Islands of the West African coast and Senegal. And actually, within about a year, they succeeded in stopping all immigrants routes from West Africa to Spain and Europe. Not to say that this is the way to cope with the present crisis but just to say, “we have in history experienced something that looks like this somewhere else and how did they solve it?” So in that way, we raise the quality of the public debate.

What other constructive journalistic frames on European migration can be explored?

Of the four constructive frames, the Human story frame seem to be waiting to be explored.

Sean Dagan Wood explained the need for more human stories,

There's a lot of underreported stories in terms of how migrants are integrating into society, what that journey means for their lives and third, people in the destination countries, in terms of their integrating, what they're bringing to their cultures of where they now live and to the economy and how that impacts people.

If we would have a more, a broader kind of framing of the issue, to really get the human stories out there as well and again challenge the assumptions around it that they kind of set the narratives that migration is generally dangerous by claim, to challenge that and to really keep it the core of the story, the human story which it should really be about.

Chapter 5: Conclusions

This research led to the following findings:

1. The journalistic frames found in constructive news framing of the European migration can be summarized in HASH: Human story, Ability, Solution and Historical.
2. The elements found in constructive news framing of the European migration which support its structure can be summarized in the WDIET method: WHAT NOW, DATA, IMPACT, EMPATHY, TRUE.
3. Constructive journalists generate these frames through a constructive mindset which is solution-focused and impact-oriented.
4. The constructive journalistic frame most present in constructive news reports is the 'ability frame'.
5. The constructive journalistic frame least present in constructive news reports is the 'historical frame'.
6. The other constructive journalistic frames that can be explored are the 'human story frame' and 'solution frame.'

Chapter 6: Recommendations

Journalists covering European migration and would like to learn how to use constructive journalism approaches can use the WDIET system in their stories. The following checklist can help them to produce not only constructive but impactful and interesting stories as well:

WHAT NOW

- Ask future-oriented questions: What now? What does it mean? How can we move forward?
- Take into account the importance of forward-looking debates. There are always different actors in a story and they might disagree on many things but they can also agree on a few things.

DATA

- Present facts using infographics to make it more understandable. Infographics allow readers to understand the issue better.
- Make sure that your story is fact-based, not opinion-based. Properly informed readers make informed choices.

IMPACT

- Think of the impact you are making while writing your story. What is your goal? Is it to create tension or to find a solution?
- Language is not neutral and has an effect on your readers. Would you use negative language or constructive language?

EMPATHY

- Migrants are human beings and are part of our common history. Take this into account when writing your story. Do not judge a group, treat them as individuals.

TRUE

- It is a journalist's job to present 'the best obtainable version of the truth' (Ulrik Haagerup, 2016) and to be able to do this, think full picture – does your story present all sides? All sides mean the negative, the positive and those in the middle. Everyone has a fair point to share. Make sure that your story carries all points.

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Appendices

Appendix 1: Interview with Cathrine Gydensted, Director of Constructive Journalism, Windesheim

Interview took place March 10, 2016 at Windesheim University of Applied Sciences in Zwolle, The Netherlands

Chared Verschuur (CV): Let's start with you as a Constructive Journalism practitioner. How you came about connecting constructive journalism with positive psychology. How you started this.

Cathrine Gyldensted (CG): It all begins with my own personal experience, meeting a source, a homeless woman in Washington DC who was part of a story that I did when I served as a US Correspondent there. She was the one who opened my eyes to how we in news coverage tend to frame things in very specific ways, tend to grow more victims than are really out there and we tend to also grow crooks or bad guys because of the way we view sources and the way we interview them. So we had these labels in journalism. But this homeless lady suddenly has some other answers than just being a victim. I realized in the interview that I was doing with her that my questions generated her thinking. She suddenly got new perspectives, got to talk about the learning she has experienced. Got to talk about the personal growth that she had experienced. Or the higher meaning that she had found in her difficult situation. I noticed that it was because I asked those questions that she came up with those answers.

CV: So those are results of your questioning, your kind of questioning?

CG: Yeah, but the reason why I started to ask her other questions was that she said something about having learned something. And I got curious about that. She answered me and then I asked another question follow-up and then she answered me and so forth. And up here I could see that it was my questions that generated her thinking and understanding of it. It's not like she had that already, it was my questioning that generated her reflection around it. So maybe she had the first constructive answer down here but she didn't know that she had a lot more to add. It was the question that I asked that generated that. So that experience got me to think about what is it that we put out in the world, how are we portraying the world, how does that affect citizens' view of what is possible. Do we teach helplessness? Do we create more victims? And I think we do. What are the repercussions for society when we do that? It started a whole circle of reflections on that.

CV: And then?

CG: That violates my personal view of why I wanted to be a journalist because I wanted to portray the world accurately. That's one of my core values. So when I saw that I didn't do that, I wanted to change. So that's why. I saw that my reality collided with a core value I had and then I wanted to change that. And the answer with positive psychology was, then I started to think, well who knows something about you know, well-being, and things that go well, and not being a victim, growing from adversity, who knows something about this part of human universe and the answer was the researches in positive psychology. I didn't know that there was a scientific domain like that before but it was because I wanted to learn from the ones who investigate this to become a more, you could say, knowledgeable journalist. That's why I took the master's degree. That master's degree was focused for people

who have another profession, who takes that degree and use what they learn back in their profession. So it was well-suited for someone like me but they had never had a news journalist there before and I don't think that they have had anyone after. Usually, you have health professionals, coaches, business people, managers, lawyers, I mean all kinds of professions taking this master's degree but journalists are you know, I think they should. Because it really expands your outlook on the world.

CV: Didn't you start questioning everything that were taught us in journalism school when you took that master's?

CG: Yes. You know, objectivity. Keeping power accountable. Portraying the world accurately. I mean, many of the core values I think are faulty in journalism.

CV: In your book, you constantly mentioned that "We want to portray the world accurately but which part of the world?"

CG: Yeah, I mean, if that's a value then you should definitely know about what positive psychology brings into human existence. Right? You would have to know about that in order to portray it.

CV: But we're not taught that (in journalism school).

CG: But I think we should be. Because some of the mistakes in news journalism as it is today with the overly negative skew stems from the methodology we're taught but also stems from journalists' knowledge of the world. So we just don't know about what's out there. We just don't know that people don't have to be victims of something. We just don't know that

you have to have post-traumatic stress every time you experience trauma so if you don't know that, you tend to over report on what you know. You don't know that something else exists and you think this is, this is reality. And you don't know what's out here.

CV: What I observed when I was practicing journalism was that I liked these stories -- that people overcome something -- but they are treated as secondary news reports. They're not as important. Negative news always goes to the first page.

CG: That's changing. That pattern is starting to change. It's true.

CV: Have you seen news reports about the European migrant crisis where Constructive Journalism is being applied?

CG: If I have seen it? (CV: You've shown me the Economist article.) That's a very strong example. The Economist, they're acknowledging that this is a huge problem. But they're also looking at how it can be solved. And another constructive element in that story is the use of data. So they have like an infographic. They use data to give a bigger overview of a complex situation so putting things into perspective. The use of data in infographics is a very strong constructive element.

CV: That's an eye-opener for me because when I read the article, I thought that they are just recognizing the migrant crisis as a European problem. That's what stuck with me.

CG: What you're telling me now is that you're getting ideas of how it could now even be more improved. That story. That it could even be more improved if you make an infographic taking it into a bigger context than the European one -- absolutely. So that's a

good idea.

CV: So should they broaden it?

CG: They could definitely do that but maybe they chose just the EU lens but you're right, you could expand it by doing what you say. It just tells me that you see the potential, right?

CV: Yeah, because it's not just a European problem?

CG: It's true.

CV: Do you have other examples?

CG: I think, and now I talk for Danish media which is the media scene I know best, I think we are starting to see more constructive coverage. It has been moving from “look at all the drowning migrants” to also trying to look for “now they're here, now what, what now? how can they be a benefit for society? if at all?” so I think, time wise, you see nothing in the beginning, almost nothing. Now I think you do because most media tend to realize, “this is reality, what do we do about it?” So that forces them into some kind of solutions-focused brainstorming. But it's not hundred percent and I don't think it should be because there are also a lot of problems with having a lot of migrants in your country and so on and they should be addressed I think, also. But I think you see more elements or you can say constructive story angles now than before.

CV: From your observation, where do these journalists put the spotlight?

CG: In constructive stories? It's the 'what now', “what could be a benefit for our society” doing this what you say “how could they strengthen our country's societal structure”, “how can they be a positive addition to our society?”

CV: And what I told you earlier that it is most of the time about the labor force. Or contribution to the labor force.

CG: You could definitely add something to that coverage by, just by your idea of breaking out of it because that's a new label. That's a new label that we put on them.

CV: What do you mean by “new label”?

CG: If you look at them only as a labor force and you put them on a shelf where they can only be laborers, they cannot be highly-qualified so and so and so. I honestly don't know if any of the migrants that we have in Denmark – what level are their education? Do they come to our country with skills or is it something that the Danish society should take on? I would need to be more knowledgeable about that to give you a more precise answer.

CV: Personally, how do you feel about that, when these migrants go to Denmark? To your country?

CG: I'm in the middle. Because in Denmark we see a split. We see the ones who really fear and hate that they're there and then we see an over humane group that says “everybody come in” and “you escape war and bombs and deaths so we should open our arms”. So you kind of have these two camps. I see that some of these arguments over here correspond to my values but I also think we cannot open our doors to everybody and see our own society break

down. So I am really in the middle. And I would love to see journalism reflect that because I think that's actually where the majority of citizens are. But because of the way journalism functions, we know most about this camp (drawing) than this camp drawing). And not about this in the middle. And that's a mistake because that's where the majority is, I think.

CV: And that's what constructive journalism is trying to do?

CG: Yeah, to shed light on the middle ground. (CV: Not on the over humane approach?) No, because that's overly positive you could say. And not taking into account the real problems that there might be with opening your borders to everybody.

CV: Is there a structure when presenting a news story in constructive journalism style when its crisis reporting like the migrant crisis?

CG: Can you say what you mean when you say structure?

CV: Like what you told me earlier that you should present the problem and then you should present the solution. Is that it or is there more?

CG: That's a good question.

CV: Like, there are also news stories where they would present the problem for the first one minute or for the last 10 seconds, they would present the solutions. Is that constructive journalism?

CG: I would have to see more good examples to be able to make a judgment on that because I think for the narrative to be trustworthy, for the journalism to be trustworthy, you

would need to have the problem in there. To understand where we're coming from.

Otherwise, you don't have a narrative arc in your story, you don't know why it's important to find solutions so you really need to have the conflict or the crisis or the problem in your story in order to make it relevant. That's my belief. How is it percentage-wise... I don't know how... I think... well, studies are showing or suggest the ending of something, just the ending of a story, the last 10 seconds or the last paragraph, is actually enough to create engagement in the reader or change their attitude or mindset on something.

CV: So it doesn't have to be 50-50?

CG: I don't think so. I think it can be done in every way. But of course, at the heart of it, you would need to have the facts, it would need to be solid and all of that. But maybe if we do research on it, we'll know more. Is it 50-50, is it 90-10? What do audiences deem as trustworthy coverage of something? Because in my master's thesis where I tested different versions of the same article, from overly negative to more balanced to overly positive, there the participants in my study pointed that all said, and they didn't know what kind of calculation we've done, but the overly positive versions were deemed untrustworthy but that makes sense, they were untrustworthy. It was about the homeless situation in the US inspired by that lady and of course it's not all easy when you're homeless and you just lost your job so they deemed it untrustworthy and for good reason.

CV: And which was the most trustworthy for them?

CG: The one that had the peak end version where you had like an emotional peak meaningfulness and then the ending of the story. The last paragraph was something that gave

inspiration or show the path forward. That version was deemed as quality journalism, trustworthy and engaging. But again, if I would do the study today, I would try to test other versions because my knowledge of it has expanded but at the time when that test was done that was the most or you could say the way to do a constructive journalistic story that seemed to get the best points with the survey participants. They didn't know what the story versions were – they were just article 1, 2, 3, 4, 5.

CV: From your study of constructive journalism, should we call it a "migrant crisis" or "refugee crisis" or "migration situation"? Or was it already a negative approach to name it that way?

CG: Crisis is a word that gives you that idea that it is a crisis. I believe very much in the power of the words that we use. You can actually measure people's emotions change when you say “migrant crisis” vs for example, “migrant situation”. And that's the power of words, right? No I think it has an effect on what you call things. Definitely.

CV: So what should we call it? From a constructive journalism approach? Should we be calling it something else?

CG: Well I think “situation” is definitely more neutral.

CV: And constructive journalism is neutral?

CG: Balanced. It's here in the middle. If you say crisis opportunity or crisis ah... migrant. What would you use to make it overly positive? Migrant what? The big migration.

CV: The great migration?

CG: The great migration is too positive, right? But “the big migration”, maybe that's a good headline. The “big modern”, the “big EU”, the “big (CV) European migration”. Something like that. You know what I mean? But then again, I don't think it's realistic to get the media to act differently on that. But it's an interesting discussion.

CV: I also read the article of Rutger Bergman (De Correspondent) about that, the effect of calling it a crisis.

CG: And then you label it as such. Yeah, I love Rutger, I think he does great work. And I think he has a great point. And I think it should be discussed but I don't know. I don't know if journalism will come to a level of consciousness that we will see that change. I'm not sure. Because that happens very fast. But maybe, maybe. But I think it's important. The use of words really have an impact. Absolutely.

CV: Why should we, why should journalists shift to that thinking? What are the benefits?

CG: Well, the benefits are, if we label it differently, our thinking shifts. Our thinking into the topic shifts. And you start to think more constructively. That's the power again of words. If you call something a crisis, that will inform your brainstorming around it, your story angles, the way you interview. It starts already with the headline. And how we have read something. That's gonna pollute or influence everything from there. The negative skew starts there. (CV: We're going to brainstorm about the migrant crisis.) Yeah, that informs the thinking around it.

CV: That's a good one. Should we rebrand it?

CG: Yeah. If you say "the big EU migrant..." what did we call it?

CV: The big EU migration.

CG: The big EU migration. That opens up something else. In my mind, when you say that, I'm thinking more possibilities, more solutions, more... it naturally just feeds a more constructive thinking. Just from the headline. So I think, you know, there's big power in what we call things.

CV: How has constructive journalism affect you personally? I discovered constructive journalism the last part of last year and it already changed the way I think.

CG: I can tell clearly. It's the reason why I want to continue in journalism. After I realized my own framing of the world in a more diseased-oriented way, I just didn't want to continue that. I couldn't continue that. That's really... it was the end... or something new to add into journalism. So it's the reason why I want to continue in journalism. It's that big a thing. I am inspired by it. I get really excited about the potential for journalism. But also on a bigger view on the potential for the world. But it's also difficult to work with because you, it's challenging me personally because when you are challenging the way journalism sees itself, its values and methodology, then you meet a lot of pushback, or so. That's the hard part about it. You know that my old colleagues, some of them think that I've gone crazy or you know, they look odd when I meet them. They don't know what to say. So that's the other side of the coin. They're afraid. They're not curious enough to understand what it is. You know what I

mean? But I guess, people, smart people say that's what happens when you pioneer something. Or you challenge a profession to do something differently. It comes with the territory. That's the other side of the coin. That you really have to struggle, struggle, struggle and repeat the arguments and you know, be prepared for what's coming here. But then you also have conversations. I get an email from someone like you or being here at the university, see my colleagues taking the idea and building it and seeing many companies being interested in it. It's so definitely moving into the right direction. If you asked for my personal view, it's giving me meaning, in my professional life but also my personal life. It also takes a lot of hard work. That's my honest answer.

CV: Yeah because I see that you fly in and out every week?

CG: It's a big investment but I have to say that after having realized what's wrong and how it could be better in journalism, I cannot do anything else than pursue it. There's no real... I'm not questioning it. It just has to be like this. And it is, so that's interesting.

CV: It is interesting. Just like I told you, I attended the constructive journalism workshop in London, I was a journalist in the Philippines before and I miss interviewing people.

CG: Well, you are also a good interviewer.

CV: Thank you. Well, I did miss going out on the field, interviewing people and knowing what their stories are so I'm doing freelancing now for Philippine TV but I want to do this because of the constructive journalism aspect. That's what I want to do, I want to

inspire people and not just help them to be negative.

CG: And you don't want that? That's not why you were there?

CV: No, I didn't want that.

CG: That's exactly. And I think, with colleagues in journalism, I'm not sure if we can win over everyone. I think there are always be (sic) a percentage of journalists who will stay, what they call negative. They call it a watchdog and I'm like, we can still be the watchdog in constructive journalism but they just don't realize like how – the connection. They don't want to realize the connection.

CV: We don't have to win over them, right?

CG: No, I don't think that any place in journalism, we have 100% agreement on. You always have a percentage who definitely not (agree). But maybe 80% of journalists will, if they take the time to open their ears and their thinking, they get it. Because all the masterclasses I've done for the past 5 years in newsrooms where I had time to invite them into discussion and then reflection on their work, nobody, nobody, has gone from that masterclass saying “this is bullshit”. If you start to reflect on it yourself and you look at the interviews you've done and the stories you've done, you see it. You see it. So it's about taking the time, having the time to really make the point and make people reflect themselves. The journalists to reflect themselves. Then I experience that they suddenly get it. But what happened to the workshop that you attended that you would regard as the highlight, something that was important for you?

CV: For me? That there are already a lot of networks doing it. And it was useful for

me to know that there are editors interested in the stories, that you can pursue it, that it's not an end game.

CG: My personal view is, and we have this discussion now at the university, should you label it as constructive journalism or should you just pitch a story that has elements of constructivity in it but it's just a good story? There are different positions on that and I'm not really sure what is the right answer because there are regional media in Denmark who are actually branding themselves on doing it. It's part of their image. PR.

CV: Do they say constructive journalism?

CG: Yeah, they do. They do. Sometimes in the newspaper they have a stamp and they say, "solutions", or "this is what others do", they kind of make an infographic around, point out of it. Because they say that they know that their readers are looking for this and they want it to be part of the newspapers' image. And then you'll have other approaches where a news editor will say, "Well, we just think it as a part of a comprehensive whole in our language behind the newsroom. We talk about the constructive elements, the stories, but to the viewers, it's just a story.

CV: They don't recognize it?

CG: No and maybe you shouldn't label it. And I'm like, "Let the media individually decide what they think is the best approach."

CV: And for you, you don't think so?

CG: I think there's something smart in the one thing that you brand yourself as such

but then again, my overall ambition with this is that it would be part of the way journalism functions. Overall.

CV: It's just good journalism.

CG: Yeah so we have a name for it now because we work on it very systematically but it should, in the end just be integrated with the way journalism functions.

CV: So that's the... way you see the future?

CG: The end goal. But then again, there are elements in this work that is really new to reign. That adds something that is new to journalism.

CV: Can you give some examples?

CG: The co-creation with audiences. De Correspondent does it very well. The way that they co-create, that's the word they use, the journalistic stories, with their audiences. The way they take them in, the story idea. It's because their platform online is built around this that you as a journalist correspondent have your garden, they call it a garden, and you follow this correspondent and you go into the correspondent's garden and see what plants are in there today, what stories. And then you have, you could say, the seed is the story idea, then you have a plant, it's a story that's being developed, then you have a tree, maybe that's the final story. And then over here with the seed, they call it the *oproep*, outcry, an announcement where they invite you in, you know if you know something about this, if you have information, please contact our correspondent.

CV: Should it be like that with the migration issue?

CG: I think it would be fantastically interesting. So that's, back to my point, that's a new piece into journalism. That has constructive (capabilities). You know, you're strengthening your conversation and your interaction with the citizens in a very concrete way. It's not one way communication. It's really (doing it) together.

CV: There was a Nieman report about co-creating stories with scientists. Does that work the same way? They were proposing: Is this the next step to journalism, co-creating with scientists, but I thought, well, that would be one-way approach because, is that the only researcher researching this?

CG: I know there's a site called The Conversation where it's maybe what you talked about, that's where scientists work together with journalists on communicating what they do, I think, but maybe that's not what you're talking about. But in my world, I think De Correspondent is doing it really, really well but of course it's because they built their online platform around this idea. It's part of their fundamental vision on how they want journalism to be and we are their example. They inspire others.

CV: And they're very independent. They don't have sponsors.

CG: No big money interests. No ads and so on. Another element of constructive journalism that I think really adds new dimension to journalism is going from, if we can, go from cover incidents to cover something complex in a systemic way, meaning that you create, you use a data, you use a big data on something to create like a graphic or interactive overview of a story. So you click on that and you see the connections and you see the Dutch

problem here, the Dutch situation here, European here, Global here. That way to story tell has a lot of constructivity in it because it shows you connections, it shows that things are interacting with each other and it shows nuances and gives citizens better information to act on something.

CV: How does constructive journalism fall into journalism? Would you call it a genre, would you call it an approach, how would you call it?

CG: It's just journalism. It's not a genre but a mindset. It's the fundamental outlook on the world that you want it to be more comprehensive. You want it to be more complete. So for me it begins in the head of the journalists, the outlook we have, the mindset we have and from there, everything follows. And I know that there are some people in the profession who works on this and says it's a genre and they just wanna put it in as say new course or a new minor. In my view, that's not the best approach because then you kind of plaster it on to something and it sometimes becomes odd because I don't think you can force it to everything necessarily. It should be all on the overall fundamental thinking of the journalist. That's what I advocate or teach. And that's also what we decide in this university to do curriculum-wise. Not to create a specific course called constructive journalism but to implement the methodology and tools into journalistic ethics, interview techniques, investigative reporting, foreign news coverage, in the existing courses, you add some of these missing elements. That's something that I have been a force behind because I think that's how it should be done and not a specific course down the line where you suddenly tell the students, "Ah forget what we told you down here in the ethics or in the tools of journalism because now we know something else." And then they'd be confused and say, "Why did you teach me about

objectivity down here and now you tell me two years on that journalism is never objective. And so on.” They will struggle with it so I'm trying to see, it happened down here in the beginning where we teach the values of journalism.

CV: You said that it can't be applied to everything but can it be applied to the migrant crisis? Or the big EU migration?

CG: Let me sum up what I think where it could be applied: It could definitely be applied in the story angles, how we cover these migrants. To see them as victims or people with resources. Do we see them as someone who's lost everything or someone that brings skills or resources or inspiration or anything else? So expanding our view on these human beings, sources, is first step. And if you expand that, it's gonna inform and inspire the questions you ask, so the interviewing. That's one place to start. But also, there's another source that journalism use here. The evil politicians. Or the politicians who have concerns or fears or whatever. I think in constructive journalism, you also work on how you interview those because there's probably a good reason behind the fear. Try to investigate that in a serious way. Why is it? What is that an expression of? So we stop acting a polarizers and start to shed light on the middle ground. And I think also, in the data use of the coverage of the migrant crisis, there's a lot of constructivity to be gained. Back to the example of The Economist and then you came with the idea of putting it into an even bigger context. Why not give me an infographic about the level of education? What is the real picture here? Where are these people education-wise? What countries are they coming from? What are the context between it? So I get a more clear overview as a reader. The sincerity of the problem. Or the potential of the migrant so-called crisis. Use data better and then facilitate a more future-

oriented discussion and debate around it. One, we have decision-makers meeting in the studio.

CV: How do we do that?

CG: First of all, just to realize that we should add questions that look ahead but I think the best way to do it is of course to start the conversation with the problem as we talked about but then move it to what lies ahead. What now? What kind of visions could we have for society in the situation? How can it be achieved? What steps should be taken? Will you do it? When will you do it? Those kinds of questions that drives the thinking and the answers to the future in a productive way. And if I am to draw it, this is the problem this is the past, this is the future. Most debates around the migrant crisis tends to look at everything that happened, the bombings, the terrible things to they're here in our country and then time's up. You kind of end, you have the focus here (past). A constructive tv debate would start here (past), we need to understand where they're coming from. And why they're migrants. We need to understand something down here. We also need to understand the challenges and the problem but most of the time would be spent up here. Most of the time of the discussion of the debate would be spent up here (future).

CV: But we've been spending it here (between past and present).

CG: Yeah, that's the classical debate format around the migrants.

CV: That's an interesting conceptual framework.

CG: Do you know what I mean? So this is where the constructivity lies. To have that happening (future-oriented), instead of that happening (past and present). So those are very concrete ideas.

CV: So what would have happened if every news report would have applied constructive journalism angle to the big European migration? First of all, it wouldn't have that branding.

CG: Now I'm only speculating but for the sake of the discussion and the exploration of the topic, I will say what I think. I think it would create less of a cleft between populations within our countries where we don't have a pro-camp and an against-camp shooting at each other so it will act more mediating. Create less fear, create more creativity, create more solutions-oriented thinking in a population or amongst decision-makers. The way that we cover it now tends to foster a lot of negative emotions around it: the fear. And we know from psychology that that closes down your outlook or your world view and if you do it more constructively, you will create less fear and more positive thinking, creativity, possibilities, solutions in the society. And I think that's what we need. So I think that is what constructive journalism could add if it was used systematically and in a methodological way.

CV: Do you think that it is a good method/approach for crisis reporting?

CG: Absolutely. And just from a journalistic point of view, it should be applied because you would want to portray the world accurately. You would want to give a more precise reporting of what's going on. So just from a journalistic point of view, that's why you should do it, in my view. But on a more societal level, some go into journalism because they want to create a better world. If you're one of those people in journalism, of course, you must be attracted to this kind of thinking. As you yourself said, you wanted to inspire.

CV: Not just help them be depressive.

CG: Yeah. Yeah. For me, I didn't want to teach helplessness and I suddenly realized that that's probably what I did and I wanted to change that. So that attracted me. But I think you can get many answers from individuals who are active in this domain. What exactly is it that made them resonate with it. Either a personal experience or something that happened in journalism or that they see that it strengthens their own values of why they went into this profession.

CV: I'm thinking of getting in touch with Rutger Bergman.

CG: You should I think he's super smart. Very interesting guy. What's more interesting about him is that he's a historian and he's using that in the way he does journalism. And that's creating you know the innovative mix.

CV: He makes the connection.

CG: Yes. He does.

CV: Because if you don't have a historical background of things, then you wouldn't know why they happened.

CG: Exactly and he always finds things in history that inspires his overall premise of the story that he's writing so he's using two domains in a very expertly (sic) way. In a brilliant way where he gets novel story ideas, coverage and meaning and reflection out of it for everybody who reads it so that's great but you know, you realize, for me, it's journalism and positive psychology that creates this new domain in here so it's just a good idea I think to make the connections between two domains.

CV: I think it's brilliant because we were always busy with... this is innovative... we're using mobile, technology. And then we're saying journalism is dead. Maybe that's not the reason.

CG: I think so. The reason why constructive journalism is growing is partly because of journalists' own wish to become more comprehensive and better journalists but also because Huffington Post and other media companies are seeing that it attracts a new audience. Or older audience return. They see that there's a potential audience for this. People are interested in it. And we have one study. I think it's the BBC who did one study that strongly suggested that young viewers would like to see more constructive journalism in terms of "show me a path forward", "tell me what can be done", "where we're headed", "what are the solutions?" That inspired Danish and national TV2 to relaunch their evening news.

CV: So from this domain and the big EU migration perspective, are there stories we're missing?

CG: Back to how we portray people, I think we miss stories around the potential that these people carry with them, the resources that they have, examples of communities we've seen an upward spiral from. An influx of migrants maybe not now but in the past, what did it take, why did it work, what needs to be overcome to make it work, those are all constructive story ideas or stories that are missing.

CV: Migration has been going on for a long time. There are other stories where it worked.

CG: Yeah. But I think you should also be critical around it. Is it easy? If it's not easy, what needs to be done to secure the success of migration and does it have anything to do with how one culture meets another. I've lived in the US for several years. There they are very happy about the Vietnamese who came but some say that it's also about the Vietnamese culture and attitude. They're very... they take initiatives, they create their own jobs, they don't wait and see, they help themselves and we have all the migrants who have another attitude and of course you should be accurate around that and look into that and be conscious that you're not labeling people. Try to not see them as one big group. Try to make individual distinctions.

CV: Is journalism ready to do that?

CG: Some journalists are. Some. You and others. Some won't. In journalism we have someone who's lazy and wanna do what they've always done and someone who's not lazy and wanna expand their methods and they'll do it differently so again that's also on an individual level.

CV: I see Constructive Journalism as a revolution in journalism but it does require journalism schools to change the mindset. Also of professors teaching journalism. Is journalism ready to take this on? Now? Are you aware of other schools doing this aside from Windesheim?

CG: I think that the fact that Windesheim is taking this step is hugely important because then you start a movement. You start a ripple effect. When they see what's coming out of this and secure the quality, the knowledge and so on, I think it will inspire others to

follow. In Denmark, there are two schools who are now looking at what's happening here and then they will maybe get the ambition to follow. You always need someone to start it and that's what Windesheim has done institutionally and in journalism education-wise but come again in two years... Already now I know, I get emails from other schools saying can you talk more about what's happening there and what's the content and how do you do it and so on and that's starting the ripple effect right now.#

Appendix 2: Interview with Ulrik Haagerup, Director of News, DR Broadcasting, Denmark

Interview took place on March 21, 2016 via Skype.

Chared Verschuur (CV): I'm Chared and I'm doing this research about constructive journalism in European migration. I'm doing a framing analysis. I read your book and I believe that you'd give me valuable insight for my research. I would like to begin with your position, just for the record.

Ulrik Haagerup (UH): I'm Director of News at DR News. DR is like the BBC, it's 1/10th of the BBC with 100% of its problems. We are 500 approximately in the news department, doing radio, tv, online. In the next 24 hours, over 83% of Danes will get news from DR. We broadcast TV news in all channels – online, mobile, social media, 5 different radio broadcasts every hour. That's about it. And some foreign affairs programs as well.

CV: And you've also been the perpetrator of constructive news in Denmark, right? Can we call you the Father of Constructive News in Denmark?

UH: Yes.

CV: How did you start with the practice of constructive news?

UH: It came gradually from when I was a reporter myself at the newspaper. I was frustrated that the Danish government and the opposition couldn't agree on anything. Even though they might agree on a lot of things. They mainly talk about the few things they disagree about and I realized that one of the reasons why they did that was that they were in a

deadlock, they weren't doing anything. And that was because of the media. Because they're talked into the news criteria of media. Because all they want is to get on the news. And in doing so, they had to talk about their disagreements, the crooks, victims, drama, conflict. Or creating it. Because if we play, in the media, if we use tabloid journalistic criteria, so will the politicians. Politics will turn into tabloid. And that might not be very good for solving the problems of society. So I thought that if I could change my role a little bit and try for once, not to find the hole in the cheese but cover the cheese instead and maybe facilitate a debate about a better tomorrow, then I could be benefit a bit more to society than I did by conducting my responsibility in a traditional way. While I was trying to experiment a little bit with that, and further did that when I was editor-in-chief of the same newspaper and later chief of a regional newspaper.

CV: When was this? When did you start?

UH: The first experiment started in the mid-90s. In 2005, we started at this regional newspaper. We started to, instead of covering only the problems in that area hit hard by globalization, we started to raise the question: "how should we make a living?" We made a big series about that and trying to also see the opportunities of that area and not only its problems. What do we have here? Yes, we have very less educated people. Yes, factories are closing down. Farming industries are doing very poorly but what are the attractions of this area? How could we... we did several things there. We made one giant competition. Giving a big prize out to the best idea to help that area. We focused on people's ideas. We did a big series about tourism and ended up finding out that these different groups in that region, they were mainly using up their money and resources fighting each other instead of trying to

attract tourists from all other places. Because that was one of the places that could not be exploited, that was the nice beaches, the nice nature. We put them together in a room, it was a summer vacation house for 24 hours, and tried to make them see that they have a common goal and if they stop disagreeing and start cooperating, they might join forces and do something bigger together. So by changing our role, and we were broadcasting that on radio and tv online, the whole region was actually following this. By changing that, we could actually make them listen to each other and understand better and maybe cooperate. I think that's where it all started.

CV: How are you applying this now at DR?

UH: We're trying to... we use it just like another tool in the toolbox. Twenty-five years ago, the new concept was case stories, the idea that journalism should not only be exposing experts and politicians but we could also include ordinary people and making them relevant. That idea of cases was very controversial in the beginning but now every newsroom in the world will work with case stories as an element in their coverage and at DR now, the idea of constructive news has been, is just another element in our coverage. Sometimes, just today, as we are covering the terrorist attacks in Brussels, we don't start saying we have to be constructive with that. Our job is there to cover it. Probably in a day or two, we will start seeing, I mean, to focus on the key issue: how can we prevent this to happen again?

CV: So, do you agree that when something like this (Brussels attacks) happens, we cannot start with being constructive?

UH: No. What is important to understand about constructive news, it's not that we

should be constructive in any story. We have to focus on what our job is. Our job is to give people the best obtainable version of the truth. See the world with both eyes and in doing so, we should see the good, we should definitely also see the bad and you can say, traditional news like breaking news as we see it today unfolding, will mainly try to answer the questions of what, where, when. Investigative journalism will add to that and will try to answer the questions of why and who. Constructive news will add to that and ask the questions: what now? and how? So of course we shouldn't forget the answers to the questions of what and where and who and why, but we should also add to that and if we do that, we will also, we will start to focus news journalism also about tomorrow.

CV: Do you also apply constructive news in DR with regard to European migration?

UH: Yes we do.

CV: Could you give some examples of stories that you did?

UH: One story was during the big migration crisis or refugee crisis last fall, where everybody, including politicians were completely in panic over what to do about all these. We thought it was interesting to go down history to see if can we learn from this. We went to Senegal and did a story about a refugee crisis in 2006 which most people had forgotten about but in 2006, a lot, thousands of people from West Africa, went to the Canary Islands on small boats in order to get into Europe via Spain. We did the story of “how did they solve that crisis” and they did it where the Spanish government and the Senegalese government started cooperating. The Spanish government gave a lot of money to Senegal in order to prevent people from fleeing because there was development aid and they were helping in the villages

so that's about money but it was also by the joint effort controlling the waters between the Canary Islands of the West African coast and Senegal. And actually, within about a year, they succeeded in stopping all immigrants routes from West Africa to Spain and Europe. Not to say that this is the way to cope with the present crisis but just to say, "we have in history experienced something that looks like this somewhere else and how did they solve it?" So in that way, we raise the quality of the public debate.

CV: What were the reactions that you received when you published it?

UH: Most people had forgotten about this crisis, most people had forgotten about how it was solved. What happens when you do stories like that, the debate changes from fear and emotions only, prejudice, panic into something more concrete and I think that's one of the things we should have as a task in our profession. To try to apply facts, so people and even politics can be made, can make better decisions based on skills and what they know, instead of only emotions.

CV: Whenever I look for constructive news on the European migration, it's always about the immigrants being laborers in Europe. So that's where the frame is. Most of the time. And this is great because it's a different kind of solution, it's like looking into a different mirror or out from a different window.

UH: What's important though is that we should never frame it. This is one of the traps of constructive news. We shouldn't frame it as the solution. We shouldn't pick a solution and try to persuade people to pick that one. That's not our job. That would be activism or that would be politics. But we could, just as well as we facilitate debates over what is the

problem, we could, and who's to blame, we could facilitate debate about what to do about it. And that's the main issue and the truth is, people really like those stories and their reactions to those kinds of stories are much better than on traditional reporting. People share it more on social media, they talk about it more. It's engaging in a lot of ways than traditional stories which would just tell you: now, 200 000 more immigrants are on their way and then you're just panicking instead.

CV: You just said that we shouldn't frame it but an important element of constructive journalism is “solutions”. Being solutions-focused, right?

UH: It is again, asking the question: what now? And when you ask the question: what now? It's saying, we are here but what do we do tomorrow? How do we cope with this? What have other people done? What are the best practices? We frame the answers by asking new questions. And I think those are some questions we have forgotten because we didn't think it led to good journalism. But we were wrong.

CV: The negativity in journalism, we learn that in school. Who's to blame, why are we negative? Why are we more negatively-focused?

UH: I think that there are several reasons for that. It's all to do with culture, it's all with identity, and you can say at some point that journalism has been hijacked, for the last 25 years, and who has it been hijacked by? One, business school logic claiming that journalism is just another product. The business school logic is if you are a product, you should ask your customers what they want. Your goal becomes what you can measure. You can measure the amount of clicks, you can measure the amount of viewers and the amount of listeners. If

people click on girls with naked torsos, we should publish more pictures of these because they sell. How do you measure that we try to make people smarter? How do you raise the quality of the public debate? How do we measure that our job, especially in public service, is to glue the society together by telling people stories about each other? How do you measure that? If we don't take care and apply that business school logic to journalism, only, we are misled, not that it's that important but that there's somebody out there, that we just shouldn't provide stories that nobody cares about, I'm not talking about that. But I think there has been a logic because we have been in such a crisis and people have been turning their backs on traditional news that we've been saying: well then we are just a product and we should sell what we're doing. But then we miss the point of a lot of quality journalism. That is one thing. Then journalism has been hijacked by reporters or activists disguised as reporters. People have come in to our profession not in able to give people the best obtainable version of the truth but in order to try to use the media to set the agenda to push the public opinion in the same direction of their own views which is not journalism, which is activism. And then, I think one of the big problems we've been facing now especially during the migrant refugee crisis, journalism has been hijacked by the politically-correct, that we in the media, as well as in the elite of society had decided, which views do we not want to help, which views are good, which views are bad. And that has led for the last 25 years, for instance, in France, that people, the elite media, the elite political parties had tried to freeze out to ignore *Front National* and their critical views on refugees with the result that a big percentage of the population do not trust traditional media, do not trust traditional politicians because they think they have been lied to. They've not been telling the truth, they've never been involved in a debate about the demographic change in France. How many people should we let into our

country? How should we treat them? And the Fran Nacional was being left out with the result that they are now building their movement which most likely will lead that their leader will probably be one or two presidential candidates in France. You see the same thing now happening in Sweden where the elite media have tried to leave out the Swedish democrats for years not inviting them to the debates. Despite the fact they are not arguing violence, they are not arguing something which is against the Swedish law but they're arguing a policy being very critical towards the present Swedish immigration policy or the policy that led up to this crisis and you can see it in Germany as well with a big percentage of the population saying "we don't trust media" because they think "they lead us in the dark, they're not telling us really the truth" and I think these things: the business school, logic, the activists and the politically-correct has led to a trust meltdown for journalism. Constructive news is basically the idea that we have to take back journalism to journalism.

CV: Can you please elaborate more on the elite media?

UH: The elite media is the traditional news media. It is the majority of the big quality press. It's the big television stations including public service television stations, commercial television stations and there's a culture. There are things in society we find are good. There are things in society we find are bad. But we should be extremely careful of using that frame in our newsroom. We have to report on it. We shouldn't go out and say "we want now to portray refugees and immigrants as very poor people" and try to persuade people to help them. Or should pass special laws which we think would be nice. That's not journalism. We could write that in editorials. We have that but we have to be very careful to separate views from news.

CV: So if you are going to produce a news report on the migration issue, how are you going to do that? As human beings, we are all subjective.

UH: Now you are coming to the core of it. Yes we are human beings but we're also professionals and being a reporter, being a journalist, being an editor means, unless you work for an interest group paper, or you work for FOX News, your job is to help people make up their own minds by providing facts. By providing both sides of the story. And yes, you're right, there's no such things as being objective, because, who can be that? But you can try. That's the core of journalism. That is to try. To give people the best obtainable version of the truth. And we have applied to the logic 'because you can't be objective'. Because you're a human being, it's ok to fuel your own reporting with your own viewpoints. And it's not. It leads to a trust meltdown in the eyes of the general population. Because the truth is, most journalists, most editors-in-chief, they are not having the same views, they don't live the same places, they don't ride the same cars. They don't have the same standard of living as the majority of the populations we are covering. We are part of the elite.

CV: So how do we do it effectively, if we are not like them?

UH: We have to be honest about it in the discussions among ourselves. We have to dare stand in front of the mirror and take the consequence of what we see. We should be honest and we have to be. We are not doing a good enough job and that's the reason why people are fleeing to new media. Which, because for the first time, people now have alternatives, they go to Facebook, they go to Twitter, they go to whatever because we've lost the ability to be the only one to tell them about peoples' stories, about everything, everywhere

to everybody. Everybody can tell their own stories. And they do that. And if we should have a future, in society, we have to understand what is the meaning we have to create and we have to be authorities in societies where there are none left. People don't believe in the church anymore, they don't believe in the military, they don't believe in the police. They don't believe, certainly not, in politicians. Problem is they don't trust media as well. But in societies where there are no authorities left, Donald Trump runs for President. Because it's the guy with the most likes, it's the guy who shouts the most, who is most loud and rude person that will get all the attention. And that is very, very dangerous in a democratic society. That's why in the news, especially public service news, we have to remember why we're here. And we have to try to establish ourselves as authorities in societies where there are none left by knowing what we're talking about. Try to see the world with both eyes and be accurate in and honest in what we try to do and we don't try to move society in a certain direction, we believe in the democracy, which is trying to help people to understand the world better but in doing so, we have to use not only one eye but both of them.

CV: So don't you agree that we move society?

UH: Of course we move society. But we shouldn't move it in a certain way. We should try to control our own views. We should try to be professional.

CV: So there is no room for agenda-setting?

UH: We set the agenda all the time. But we should try to set the agenda to what do people think, not only what we think.

CV: Are you saying that constructive journalism is a mindset?

UH: It's a mindset. You can say that it's a very old-fashioned mindset. It is trying to take journalism back to where it belongs which is to publishers. Publishers publish their stories because they want to do good, they want to serve the community, they don't want to lead the community. They don't want to manipulate the community. They strongly believe that it's important that people make up their own minds.

CV: Being the Director of News at DR, isn't it difficult to teach your reporters this? A new mindset? How do you do it?

UH: It's a mindset thing so what we normally do, we tell stories about why do we have to do something different. We praise those who try and we assign some of the stories to some of the best reporters so it's not the youngest intern doing it. We try to boost the stories so that viewers see that they are good journalism as well. And it's assigned to the best reporters we have but definitely, it hasn't been easy. It is not something that you can just say, "now we can do it" and send out a memo and everything is fine. It takes time. It's about culture.

CV: News culture?

UH: Yes.

CV: Where do you put the lens now on European migration? I mean, for example with the Brussels bombing, they will connect it.

UH: Yes of course. But we are actually running a project right now. One week it's

about the facts, integration, how many people are here, where do they come from, how integrated are they, what is integration anyway, how many do speak Danish, what are the views, would they like their daughters to marry a Dane? Or their sons to marry a Danish girl? We base the debates about facts. So you see, is there a difference whether you come from Korea or you come from Somalia, or you come from Turkey or you come from Pakistan? What are the differences in integration level? Where in the country do they live? If we see that there's a problem when people are not really integrated, then we can start adding stories, what could we do about it? Which countries in the world are the best to integrate? People from different backgrounds. How do you do it? What are the tools in the toolbox? Which cities in Denmark are best in integrating people? What do they do different than the rest of the cities. Then we put people together in one room, meeting politicians and we try to see, “ok, now we know this, we know there's a problem, could you come up in 24 hours with a plan, a 5-point plan that can change the situation? what can you agree on?” We report that, we film, we air it and we share it with people so we can have a discussion in the whole country about this. That's the idea.

CV: If you were to name the issue at hand, would you call it the European Migrant Crisis?

UH: No, I would probably call it the Biggest European Dilemma right now. It's a dilemma because it conflicts our sense of humanity with sense of fairness, sense of economical possibilities. It really challenges a lot of things. So it's a challenge and a dilemma – about morale, about economics, about politics. And of course, it's also a crisis. When something is out of control and you don't know what to do about it, that's the definition of a

crisis. But we try not only to call it an immigrant crisis. It's a refugee immigrant crisis problem and a challenge. But also to focus on opportunities. The truth is that Europe, European women, they get too few children. So in a few years, we'll need a lot of people. And a lot of unskilled labour and where do we get it from? But can we open the borders to everybody who wants to come here? Or should we invite people and who should we invite? It raises a lot of questions. How to deal with this. We should cover all of it.

CV: Personally, what's your opinion on that? Can we take them all?

UH: I don't have an opinion on that because that would be politics. That's not my issue. I think it's an equally fair viewpoint on the political debate to be covered. If you think, we live on one planet. That borders are something artificial. That it is not fair that just because you're born behind one border, you couldn't move to wherever. That's totally fair to say that. Everybody should be allowed to go to Denmark if they want. That's fair. But it's also fair if you say, "we have borders and a nation is created because you have borders and you have people outside that border and people inside that border" and we can have a debate about "who should be allowed to come in and which demand and opportunities do we give to the people who come in?" That's also a legitimate viewpoint. And it's also legitimate if you say, "I think Denmark should mainly be for Danes and I don't want people to come in here if they are not born Danish." I'm not saying if I agree or not, I don't agree, but I think it's a fair viewpoint. And we should cover that. And it's also fair that you are scared if the borders are open and a lot of people come in who you do not know who have completely different cultural background. It's a fair viewpoint. And we should report on those fears and try to apply facts about it. Who are coming in? What are they views? Are they all terrorists? Are

they all nice looking mothers with cute kids? What are we talking about?

CV: What could have happened with this issue if we used Constructive Journalism from the very beginning?

UH: I think that if we would have done that, we would have more trust from the general population, which is important. It doesn't matter what we reported, people don't believe in it. So if we have, from the start, decided that, "Now, it is our job to show the full picture – the good, the bad, the opportunities, the challenges" -- and try not to say, "Now our job is either to tell a lot of newspapers, get a lot of viewers and reporting about the hordes of millions coming in taking our job, taking our girls, taking our money", as some tabloid newspapers did in the beginning or as a lot of elite media did later saying, "now we would absolutely be careful that we don't feel fascism so we only report on the nice stories", there would have been more trust.#

Appendix 3: Interview with Sean Dagan Wood, Editor, Positive News

Interview took place on May 17, 2016 via Skype.

Chared Verschuur (CV): How's positive news in the UK?

Sean Dagan Wood (SDW): Good. You're probably aware of the changes we've been through in the last year. Our crowdfunding campaign and relaunching. It's exciting time for us as we grow. We're getting a great response to our new magazine. I'm really pleased about that.

CV: How many subscribers do you have now?

SDW: We have 4000 subscribers to the print magazine. With a circulation of 10 000. And then we have a hundred thousand unique visitors to our website each month and 260 000 social media followers.

CV: Do you have an end goal? What's the end goal?

SDW: Broadly speaking, our purpose is to inspire a thriving world so we want our journalism to be in service to society. To our community. We want to inform people in a way that empowers them to use that information constructively whichever way they choose and leave people feeling informed and inspired and not left feeling cynical. We want to scale up what we're doing so for Positive News itself, we want to increase our audience. Our first target is to increase print subscriber levels to 10 000 and we're also looking to expanding our digital audience as well of course. First of all, I mean to get to the point of financial sustainability for Positive News itself so after our crowdfunding campaign, we create a new

business plan on what to do with that with the investment that we raised. More broadly speaking, why the cultural purpose of course is to influence a more balanced and constructive media so Positive News is doing constructive journalism in practice to show how it can be done. Of course, constructive journalism can be interpreted (sic) in different ways, manifested in different ways, so across quite a broad spectrum but with that core principle of rigorous quality journalism that brings in more positive elements as a constructive mindset so that tries to show a full picture reality and report in the world in a way that empowers people rather than potentially overwhelming people with negativity and actually then not serving society because we're leaving people with a feeling that nothing can be done and not able to use that information effectively to create, to take informed, effective choices in their lives. More broadly, we want to influence other media to bring that mindset and bring the techniques of constructive journalism into the work they do and to serve their audiences more effectively. So it's really about strengthening journalism, it's about taking the wonderful expertise, skills and potential of journalism and the valuable role of journalism in a democratic society and with bringing in more constructive journalism to strengthen its ability to serve that fundamental role in the purpose of democracy of still holding power to account, finding, reporting truth and by showing the full picture and empowering people.

CV: How did you start with the constructive journalism practice? Was it something you've done from the very beginning or did something happen that made you practice it?

SDW: Positive News was established about 23 years ago and I just got involved about seven or eight years ago. At the time I discovered it, I realized reading a copy the way that made me feel, the way it opened my mind, it suddenly challenged my whole story of the

world, the narrative of how the world is, what potentials of human beings are, what's going on in society, what's being done, what can be done and it affected how I felt as well about the world and about myself, about what's possible, so I realized that how powerful journalism was and in setting back that cultural story that we buy into whether consciously or sub-consciously. There are facts how we view ourselves and each other and view our world which then affects our behaviour so I realized that in reading stories that energized me and motivated me and showed me that there are things going on I wasn't aware of in terms of positive social environmental impact that's being created by individuals or communities or organizations both in local and international levels. I realized that the more I was exposed to those stories, the more it affected my world view and the more it affected my view of human nature and I realized that journalism as it was that the dominance of negative framing was actually holding us back. I think it was limiting the human potential. When I was reading Positive News, for me that was sparking the human potential. It was opening my mind. Personally then I felt, this has got so much power to empower positive benefits for society then I wanted to be involved in it. I realized that if we had a media that wasn't triggering fear and anger and alarm so much and that was exposing the positive change that was taking place, naturally, the more focus that would be given to that positive change and the potential for it with the constructive mindset, the more it would create a fertile ground for people to, in whatever way that individuals or organizations or societies, communities wanted, to take constructive choices, to be more informed and follow new pathways in their lives, at work and you know, without dictating what that is, without advocating anything in particular, but at the fundamental level, offering different mindsets, different ways of viewing things which would then mean that those positive development would be amplified, energized, magnified.

Because where we put our focus is so powerful. That's the kind of recognition that's really key for me. It's that power of our attention and the power of story and the power of how we frame things.

I just felt that given the challenges that we face – local, national and global levels – it's not good enough now but it just reports the problems but leaves us feeling cynical, disempowered. Yes, it's important to expose those problems of course, like that saying, it's important to hold power to account but that's not enough because we need to be informed in a way where we can respond to that constructively. And of course if the way we're reporting is driven by commercial note, that's not good enough either. I think that the media has a duty to report in a way that gives people information that they can use constructively. It's what's needed. We have to be realistic about that.

CV: If we use constructive journalism to the issue of European migration, if other news bureaus will use it, what elements do they have to add to the stories they're producing now?

SDW: I think something that the Director-General of the United Nations said recently when I interviewed him and he spoke about this issue. He was really calling for, around this issue in particular, with facts and empathy and I think that's quite telling because obviously he had a clear understanding of all the activity that was going on globally in terms of support of refugees and the migration that was taking place and both sides of the stories in terms of negative impacts and positive impacts in different countries. I would agree with him that first of all, there's a need for the facts and the full picture and the migration issue gets very siloed

into the very motive aspects of it. It's often framed through the kind of fear-based concerns. So I think, there's that need to first get facts clear about it or other positive or negative impacts on this issue and sometimes that might mean that there's a potential that the information can be a bit dry on the issue and the challenge of journalism there is really making a compelling story recognizing that this information's important, we can't just tell the easy hard-hitting short story of crime committed by migrants or whatever it is. We have to dig deep and look at the full picture. We have the responsibility to make that information interesting and exciting. So we have to work harder there because that information's important. And then, so the other aspect that the United Nations Director-General also mentioned was empathy and to me that's part of a constructive mindset as well. Framing things in a way where we are reminded that this is an issue involving human beings and that's really important. For me, getting the facts clear but then looking at, ok, where the negative impacts are, where the potential dangers and problems are associated with migration, you know whether that's about resources, population density and people's fears around crime but also we have to balance that with of course, the positive impacts such as economic benefit and the benefits on the culture and I think it's really important to look for those stories of where migration has led to positive benefit for refugees and migrants themselves and also for destination countries and that's where the human stories are really important. I think an important part of that is thinking about, looking at it from a neutral starting point with the issue then we should really be looking at what are the problems and where is the progress being made and actually, there's lots of positive stories and angles, solution-focused angles into the stories. The first obvious one being often, people who are migrating or refugees are fleeing persecution in all really difficult circumstances and they're finding a place of aid

where they can rebuild their lives, I mean that's a positive story in itself and that's kind of easily forgotten. That basic story of survival for people in their situation.

There's a lot of underreported stories in terms of how migrants are integrating into society, what that journey means for their lives and third, people in the destination countries, in terms of their integrating, what they're bringing to their cultures of where they now live and to the economy and how that impacts people. For example, we're planning a story on our next issue and we're speaking to a number of refugees who have settled in London, talking to them about their experience of being a refugee and the way we frame it is we photograph them in the place where they first felt at home. So the story is built around that feeling of being at home again, which of course is a huge thing for them to have lost that and it is a big personal journey to get started where you feel at home again somewhere else. So that's the way into the issue, into the story for us. Equally, we could take the negative angle of all about the difficult side of the story – where they are moving away from or kind of the negative, potentially negative impacts of a destination but we're looking at where the progress has been made and that. It's obviously a different way for the audience to connect to them and the story.

We also ran a story a while ago about an initiative in Berlin where some young people just started offering their spare rooms to refugees and this scheme group and of course, it's not just about supporting the refugee but people with spare rooms. They really benefit as well. They make friends, they learn, it's cultural integration and they say it's a great thing and I think, part of constructive journalism is challenging assumptions of what news is, what's important, how it should be framed and also challenging the assumption and the kind of accepted narratives that journalism buys into. For example, that the most important issues are

politics and economics. What about these loads of stuff happening at the grassroots level, just underreported, which is actually where people can relate to perhaps more directly? Rather than a large volume of political stories which encourages reactivity where people have little influence on? So I think, with things like the migration issue again and we have to challenge the underlying narratives, the assumptions in that, so, even the idea that we should have borders and in this day and age, we should be thinking about migration and predominantly, this could be a problem, where we can also totally reframe it and maybe, we need to be thinking differently about what it means to be a global citizen now in a world where we are all digitally connected and where transport is so much easier and we're efficient and things like this which could be beneficial for the world.

CV: So is being a constructive journalism a mindset or something that you learn?

SDW: You can learn it, you do learn it but from the starting point, it's definitely a mindset. The mindset's the crucial thing. The tools of journalism, they're not different from constructive journalism, it's really the core in how they're applied. There are new techniques, I'm told, that's been developed that's specifically for constructive journalism, which I'm sure Catherine Gyldensted's told you about which are being informed by things like positive psychology so there's definitely particular techniques such as interview techniques like where were asking different kinds of questions in order to find people's strengths and the language we use so we look at the language we use and not being not automatically using language that might be violent or triggering a kind of people's emotions in order to grab attention where it should not be warranted. Things like that. The thing that drives that really is the mindset. For me, part of that, the core this is, realizing the impact of journalism, the impact of framing and

the power of story, how we use story to give meaning to our lives, to connect with others, understand our world and so we have to go beyond that idea where we are just reflecting back society in journalism because we're not. We're selecting information, framing it in certain ways and that's affecting people's perceptions which of course influences their behaviour so it comes back to asking: "Why we are doing this? Why do we need journalism now? What's journalism's role? What should it be doing?" I think that if we start asking that deeper question then we start taking responsibility for the impact of our journalism and we have then to think about our mindset there. So if we know journalism should be informing people in a way it empowers them, then what's the mindset in which we are doing that if we're just focused on exposing scandal and create drama, is that the best use of journalism? Is that gonna serve people? I don't think so.

CV: So you do admit that we (journalists) do framing?

SDW: Yeah.

CV: Because there are journalists that say that we just tell it as it is. We just tell it as it happens.

SDW: Well, I think it is important for constructive journalism that we do try to learn from other fields. As I understand it, the social sciences and the kind of theories around it and the research that's been done around it makes it clear that it's an inevitable part of being a human being. Journalism itself is a whole field. We can only show a narrow fragment of reality. There's just so much information, so much happening, we have to be selective, we have to think about what drives that selection. And as individual human beings, we can't

escape the way we've been shaped by our nature and our circumstances and our influences and all the processes that go in our unconscious as well. As hard as we try and as worthy it is to try to be objective, and of course, we're fact-based, but because we use language, we can't escape the fact that language is not neutral so things are always framed and in creating stories, no one writes an entirely dry story that's purely a list of facts. No one would read it. So inevitably there is framing, there are storylines, there are emotional picks and drops. They are a means of engaging people. And every choice we make in how we do that has an impact. An important thing is to just be aware of that because it's inescapable so I think, be aware of values.

CV: Does constructive journalism use certain words to qualify as such?

SDW: Not using certain words but be aware that it has an impact so just be conscious on how you're doing it. That kind of self-awareness. And coming back to why you're doing what you're doing and let that guide how you create a story. The news values are really important and I think what's more important is being transparent about that. With Positive News for example, we're publishing stories that we think are positive so there's that clear framing but we're transparent about our purpose and we're transparent about our ownership structure, we're owned by and led by journalists, we're not for profit and we're about serving society about inspiring a thriving world through our journalism so you can read our content knowing that that's why we're doing it. It's up to you to trust it or not. At least you know where we're at. Why we're doing it. What's driving it. What our mindset is. Which newspaper is really transparent about the motives and how much their commercial incentives affect its choice of stories and so on.

CV: Do you have a group of reporters that come up with stories for Positive News?

SDW: Yeah. We work with predominantly freelance journalists and we have a small number who write for us more regularly, around 10 journalists. We work with journalists who work with other publications as well, some who work for more independent processes, some who work for newspapers, so yeah, we take pictures and we also assign content, we try to obviously cover the topics and find stories we think are most relevant and interesting and we monitor the kind of major news agenda and other news agenda but we try to not assume that that's what's important. We try to really make our own judgments about what we feel would be of interest and of use to our readers.

CV: Is it difficult to source constructive stories?

SDW: Not at all. Our main limitation is that we are small at the moment, with limited resources and of course we're trying to build a business model to show that this is a financially viable form of journalism and that people really want it which we know is the case. We can't publish all the stories we'd like to because it's important for us that we pay journalists and we do good quality journalism so we're not just gonna churn out a load of content that we've created for free as some small publishers do but no, there's so much amazing stuff going on out there, it's not hard at all. It's when you have that shift in mindset and you're looking in the right way and in the right places, it's incredible and it's an amazing story, this kind of alternative narrative of what's happening in human society because really, in terms of the kind of core pillars of our society and our social economic system, they're getting hugely challenged by new ways of doing things now and there's a myriad of

individual stories. We've been there. How people are putting forward new ways of creating local economies for example or doing healthcare or you know whatever it is, there's load out there. And the challenge really is to recognize the significance of those stories and then put them in the front page and make them into a big compelling story and suddenly then, oh yeah, that's the big story but there's these assumptions again about what's important and what people want and that mindset that needs challenging. We work a lot with freelance journalists and it's easier for them. Journalists working for institutions, it's a really big challenge for them to go against the established culture and mindset and even I spoke recently to some editors of the UK's national papers and they were saying this that it's hard to change the culture especially when newspapers are low in resources. It's harder to reallocate resources to doing something different even though at the same time, they know that they need to because they got to try new things in order for them to sustain their businesses. That's why we find through the courses that we run through the Constructive Journalism project, so many enthusiastic freelancers who were looking for different ways to do their journalism in different places to publish and when we train student journalists as well, there's so much enthusiasm for it because they're not yet into that fixed mindset of doing things in a certain way where news is the same as negative news. The more that publications start taking the constructive journalism approach, publishing more positive stories, the more that it would be done because then there's be more examples of how to do it and they will be more legitimized as a practice that is part of the journalism landscape and there's definitely a welfare of stories out there.

CV: In this business model that you have, who should change, should we start from

editors, from reports or from the journalism school?

SDW: I think it's both. I think the moment there's an opportunity to start in journalism schools before people, as I say, get ingrained in a journalistic culture that is hard to shift and also there's an issue of identity which I think is important, that being a journalist has a very strong identity to it and when people are being journalists for a long time, they have a particular identity and often that's associated with, if we take a kind of extreme, it's an investigative journalist who is holding power to account and exposing scandals and corruption and of course that is an incredibly important thing to do. That kind of polarized idea of uncovering wrongdoing the watchdog, that's a very strong identity and editors who are driving that approach, they have obviously a very strong identity they've built up around, who they are as a journalist as well and I think understandably, that's a hard thing to just shift so I think that fact is important in considering how easy it is to change our institutions.

Whereas people coming fresh into the field, their identity is there to be shaped so I think there's opportunities then to rethink what it is to be a journalist and to come back to what's really driving why you want to be a journalist which we always find a lot of commonality in people saying they went into journalism because they wanted to make a positive difference in the world and of course holding power to account is a key part of that but it's not just about that. It's about saying what you're doing empower people, inform people effectively, not leave so many people feeling cynical, world-weary. I think it's a combination. I think we'll continue to see more publications like Positive News and see journalism as diversifying, diversity of voices online particularly, there's more and more people working freelance and able to shape their own niche and pitched different kinds of publications but it's a challenge to make that pay but I think we will see more and more editors and publishers starting to look at new ways

of doing things because the business models are breaking down. So I think it's a combination of both because the media is so big and powerful that we can't ignore that impact and we have to try and work with the media institutions and find those opportunities but I think unless there is some buy-in at a number of levels across the organization in terms of journalism editors, potentially proprietors, then it's hard to shift and this is what some of the editors I've been speaking to recently at some of the UK papers were saying was the proprietorial influences strong and hard to change. So that's why ownership models are important as well and one of the reasons why at Positive News, we've created this new cooperative ownership model so that we're accountable to the people we're here to serve. What will help as well is like you've mentioned is journalists networking working together around this form of journalism supporting each other. There's a potential for collectives and cooperatives of journalists taking this approach starting their own publications and of course there's financial challenges there with making that pay but I think the change, we're gonna see the innovation from the bottom up and hopefully, that will start influencing the institutions to move in that direction.

CV: How did constructive journalism change you as a person?

SDW: When I discovered Positive News, it was around the same time as I was starting to realize how the story I was telling myself about me and my life was affecting my reality, my experience. I've always been interested in personal development. For a long time, I started learning about positive psychology and related fields and so I made the connection between what was happening in my own head in terms of how I was framing things for myself, the mindset I had and how that was affecting how I felt and how I experience life and

what was happening at a wider scale in terms of the social consciousness of collective mindset to society. How the media is a big storytelling machine that shapes that mindset, what that was doing and I thought, right, this is amazing in the same way that I can shift my perspective in framing and that affects my experience, we can do that collectively as a society. We can empower ourselves through doing that. So that was incredibly exciting. And it's interesting because obviously, working in this field, it does challenge me all the time, reflecting back on myself to look at how I'm framing things for myself and my mindset and creating and fundamentally, it was empowering because I realized, wow, as human beings, we're incredibly creative, we have the capacity to, we don't just react to what reality gives us. We're not just kind of passive being pushed around through a cause and effect mechanism and just dealing with whatever comes in front of us, we're creative human beings, we have this amazing intelligence and we can actually steer our evolution through the choices we make and that starts with a perspective of how we view things. How we interpret things and then with awareness, we can then choose how we respond and that's a very powerful thing. And so we can do that collectively as a society as well. So it's a good reminder for me all the time in the work I do that I can choose where to put my focus, I can choose how I respond, I can choose where I give my energy and attention to and I know from my experience that that affects my reality.

CV: Would this have happened if constructive journalism was consciously applied to European migration stories from the onset of the crisis?

SDW: Yeah, I think so. It would have hugely affected the situation. I think... you can see how powerful the story that the media is putting out when you look at the impact of the

photo of the toddler washed up. Of course that is a bit of negative news but that was constructive in a sense of it being exposed to reality. What was really interesting was the switch in the media afterwards. The reframing of migrants. The focus on refugees. That was a period when we saw quite a lot of positive stories. The focus was what was being done about it. How are the refugees being held and then the outpouring of compassion was amazing. And you can just see how that started affecting people's response to the issue. I think what's really significant is the way not just these, the media stories immediately impact our view of the issue but the kind of, the language it gives us and the narrative it creates, how that's then perpetuated to the conversations we have at home, in the pub, you know that we'll stop buying into those stories and of course it's not that simple but I think the impact is just really significant. So yeah if there's a more constructive approach from the start, there would be a lot more attention given to a full range of facts about the issue and it would have affected how we view migration, how we view refugees. It would affect how the resources are then given to dealing with the issue.

CV: Would it have created more understanding too?

SDW: I think it certainly would have had the potential to. If we would have a more, a broader kind of framing of the issue, to really get the human stories out there as well and again challenge the assumptions around it that they kind of set the narratives that migration is generally dangerous by claim, to challenge that and to really keep it the core of the story, the human story which it should really be about.

CV: It's interesting what you said that the story of the toddler washed up on the shore

is a constructive journalism story. Is it?

SDW: In itself, it depends how it's framed and the bigger context around it. It certainly could be part of a constructive story. That is a hard reality that exposes the scale, the tragedy of the issue and of course that has to be told but then, the question is, what next? So now the question is, right, this is a wake-up call to the children dying because families are desperate to get out of their home country because of how horrific their lives are out there. So that is a way in to open people's minds and activate their hearts and issue which is what we're trying to do with our journalism. It's then, ok, so what can be done about that? What's already been done? What are the ways forward? And that's where it can't just be token positive responses, it's not just about pity. It's about what practically can be done to change this? So that has to be about an international effort based on compassion. To deal with that situation based on justice and fairness and facts about the issue. And that's where you could then start about telling really positive stories of how refugees have been helped and how they've been integrated into societies in a way that's really benefitted their destination countries and the refugees themselves when you can start looking at so what are the, instead of the idea of more people being in a place a problem, what are the opportunities of that?

CV: When I read constructive stories about the European migration, it's always about how migrants can work for us. Is that the only thing? Or are we missing something more?

SDW: I think, we are missing a lot more. Again, that's like quoting the economic narrative first which I just don't like because that's making certain values more important than others. It's all about the economy, that that means of exchange is the best of one thing when actually it's about human beings. So I think it's important to not allow that to automatically be

the framing.

CV: So what should be the framing aside from the economic lens?

SDW: I think for example, there's this story I mentioned that we're creating. The framing is the human story of when some refugees felt at home. So that's a story of helping people feel at home. Everyone can connect to that feeling of being at home. And I think then that's a different way into the issue. Because then the assumption there is that refugees need to benefit the destination country and the economy. The assumption in there is that people want to feel at home. And that a society rather have an obligation to have a productive economy, starting point is, we want people to thrive.

CV: Do you have other examples of the stories that you're making at Positive News?

SDW: In a current issue, we also ran an infographic about the EU, about the UK's vote on being in or out the EU and we ran an opinion piece about free movement of people and this again is about challenging assumptions on the issue and our economist is not advocating being around the EU but trying to reframe the debate by saying these assumptions within this issue that the free movement of people is a bad thing. She's saying actually this is a natural part of human society, something we should embrace. Yes, there's other aspects that could be problematic or positive for being in and out the EU but the idea of free movement of people is being framed wrong and we should actually challenge that, realize that that's something that could be embraced and is always going to be a natural part of human society. So that, using that as a way into the issue for us, we didn't want to just kind of put an opinion out there whether we should be in or out. We wanted to inform people better so the way that

we felt doing constructive journalism that we could do that is to challenge the foundation of the narrative around it. So reframe it. So we present facts in our infographic and at the same time we say, in terms of how we interpret those facts, bear in mind that free movement is not necessarily the problem. Just challenging that idea of “oh, there's lots of people trying to cross the channel and our country is going to fill up.” It's not that simple.

CV: If you were to name the issue at hand, would you have named it the European migrant crisis?

SDW: That's a really good question because obviously there, crisis is a very loaded word. Of course it is a crisis because there's human life being lost. And this large-scale movement of people has caused us a huge stress on our societies, but, yeah, I don't kind of have an instant answer to that. I think it is a really provocative question. Part of me is saying, “ok, is there a solutions framing for this? would that be the appropriate framing?” I don't want to jump to that conclusion just to give an answer because obviously, there's a lot of tragedy in the story. But I think, as I've mentioned before, we do have to kind of challenge our assumptions in issues like this and think, ok, in 2016 the world is changing, continue to change significantly and we're seeing an increase in movement of people so maybe actually, because this is an ongoing issue, this is something that the United Nations Director-General mentioned to me in an interview that I mentioned earlier, he was saying that we've only seen the start of this and we will continue to see this and this may affect countries such as the UK in our lifetime in a very direct way. This isn't going away and then when you think of the fact that we do have the global interconnection that we have digitally now and then you know, for me, I start thinking, well, let's not assume that everything will stay the same as it is. Maybe

this is more an issue about movement of people in general and nations and borders and should we be questioning where that's leading in the future? So I think, I guess, it's just something to be aware of, I don't know how I'd turn it exactly but I guess it's good to recognize that we are framing it in that way.

CV: And that there should be changes in the kind of reporting of the European migration? Isn't it too late to change?

SDW: I don't think it's too late. It is where it is. We have a responsibility to question this because of the impact we're having as an industry. And as I've mentioned, it's not an issue that is going away, especially when you think about climate change – potentially the biggest issue of all considering the impacts of the dislocation of people. This is an issue that's going to grow. So I think we need to be able to deal with that in an ongoing way that isn't just about drama. There is about informing people about the issue in a way that whoever's in the position to do so, that's a small choice in their daily lives or a choice in influencing policy that we need to be informing people in a way where everyone can take the best choice as they can in that so I think we should reflect on it and continue to challenge ourselves and how we're framing it.

CV: Is there anything else you'd like to add?

SDW: I'd just add that I think when we look at the scale of the situation, it's a kind of issue that, I would like to be clear that I'm not talking about advocacy journalism but I think everyone does have a potential to play a part in this because all our choices and all our lives have impact and that I think, there's an opportunity for us as a global community to deal with

this issue effectively if we're informed in a way where there is more fertile ground for us to proactively respond to it in a positive way. The more exposure we give to positive stories around the issue, the more that it's gonna help that situation because people are gonna be inspired around their own lives to do something in response to the situation as positive whether that's just a shift in mindset or whether that's a kind of action. That's not about telling people particular actions to take or some people should take action, it's creating a space in our cultural narrative, creating a space for that possibility.#